

AI4

Final report documenting the integration of user applications at full scale

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ACRONYMS

Please, see <https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/help/glossary.html>

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable provides the final report on the integration of pilot applications and open-call use cases within the AI4EOSC project's Work Package 6 (WP6), identified as Deliverable D6.3. It consolidates the work carried out during the project, documenting how applications have progressed from initial prototypes to fully integrated demonstrators of the AI4EOSC platform.

The report covers both pilot use cases, defined at the outset of the project, while also including contributions from a limited number of open-call use cases. Each use case is examined in terms of its final integration into the platform and its contribution to the validation of services, ensuring consistency with project objectives and relevance for the wider community.

In addition, the deliverable addresses the feedback collected from users throughout the project, covering both overall impressions of the platform and more detailed comments on individual services and tools. It also highlights the strategies used to engage users, promote collaboration, and encourage knowledge sharing within the community.

1. - INTRODUCTION

The [AI4EOSC project](https://ai4eosc.eu)² is designed to deliver advanced services that support the creation and deployment of Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) applications within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). By integrating various components and real use cases into the platform, the project ensures that the developed services are validated in practice and aligned with the needs of scientific communities.

This final deliverable presents the consolidated outcomes of the integration process, showing how the platform's components, pilot applications, and selected open-call use cases have been combined into fully integrated demonstrators, demonstrating the maturity and functionality of the AI4EOSC platform.

1.1 - SCOPE OF THE DOCUMENT

This deliverable focuses on the integration progress made since the previous report, documenting how the platform components, pilot applications, and selected open-call use cases have been consolidated. It summarizes the development and integration milestones, as well as the feedback received from users, highlighting improvements, lessons learned, and the overall readiness of the AI4EOSC platform to support the EOSC community.

² <https://ai4eosc.eu>

1.2 - STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

The document is organised into the following sections:

AI4EOSC platform for users: Provides an overview of the AI4EOSC components and services exposed to platform-users, described from a user perspective, i.e., what features and functionalities they bring, and how they facilitate the user experience.

Integration of final applications: Presents achieved results and findings of use cases of the platform, which are described in detail: e.g., data curation, model development and validation, service delivery, integration with the platform, main findings and outlook. The section also includes a final implementation of the leading-by-example application, the progress and achievements of the open-call users, and integration of the AI4Life BioImage Model Zoo.

User feedback: The section analyses general user satisfaction with the platform and the detailed user feedback about the usage of various platform services and tools.

Conclusion: A concise summary of key findings and of the integration of user applications and user experience.

2. - AI4EOSC PLATFORM FOR USERS

The AI4EOSC platform advanced significantly over the course of the project and many new features and capabilities were developed and made available for the platform users. In the following we review the tools and services exposed to users and describe them from a user perspective. A full catalog of the platform services can be found in our D3.4 “AI4EOSC Catalogue of Services” ([Calatrava Arroyo et al. 2025](#)).

2.1 - AUTHENTICATION AND AUTHORISATION INFRASTRUCTURE (AAI)

The platform offers a central authentication and authorisation interface to the majority of services. This system is based on Keycloak³. Keycloak federates different identity providers, which allows for an easy onboarding of new external communities with their own authentication systems.

2.2 - STORAGE

The storage solution in the AI4OS/AI4EOSC ecosystem is a dedicated Nextcloud⁴ instance, specifically designed to support users working with large datasets and AI model training workflows. Each user is granted a free 500GB storage quota, which is still possible to expand, if necessary. Nextcloud enables users to both store and share data, and facilitates direct access to storage from within their AI4OS deployments. There are two primary methods for accessing Nextcloud files from within deployments:

³ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

⁴ <https://nextcloud.com/de/>

- Copying files to the user deployment hard disk, using tools like rclone⁵ or by copying from the `/storage` path, which can be beneficial for faster disk reads but is limited by disk capacity of the user deployment.
- Mounting the user's Nextcloud directory inside the deployment at the `/storage` path. This sets up a virtual file system that provides network-based access to Nextcloud storage through the WebDAV protocol. This approach is recommended for handling large datasets exceeding the disk space of user deployment.

This integration ensures seamless data handling and sharing while supporting the needs of advanced AI workflows within the AI4EOSC platform.

2.3 - AI4EOSC MARKETPLACE

The Marketplace on the AI4EOSC platform is a comprehensive catalog where users can discover, share, and access a wide range of AI modules and tools. It serves as the main hub for published modules, including pre-trained models, trainable models, tools, workflows, and modules developed both within the platform and by external contributors. The Marketplace lists all available AI modules and tools along with corresponding metadata. This includes specialized tools like the Federated Learning server, general-purpose modules that can be retrained on user data, and a generic base module known as the AI4OS Development Environment, which serves as a starting point for creating new deployments.

An initial version of the Marketplace is accessible to general (unregistered) users with limited deployment options, but still detailed views for all modules provide additional information such as a brief description, module categories, links to the code repository, Docker images, and, if available, dataset details. This structure facilitates easy discovery and use of AI resources within the AI4EOSC ecosystem.

2.4 - TRY-ME

With the Try button, users can create temporary deployments (for 10 min, see [Figure 2.1](#)) via the Gradio⁶ interface. These temporary deployments enable users to try inference of each existing module on the marketplace. For this the user needs to be authenticated. This provides a flexible and user-friendly way of interacting with a module.

⁵ <https://rclone.org/>

⁶ <https://www.gradio.app/>

Figure 2.1: Example of the 'try' button on the general module YOLO

2.5 - CVAT ANNOTATION TOOL

The Computer Vision Annotation Tools (CVAT⁷) is an open-source tool for image and video annotation provided as a cloud or self-hosted application. CVAT supports multiple video and image formats, as well as 3D data. CVAT offers a wide range of annotation tools enabling annotation of different shapes such as rectangles, polygons, polylines, skeletons or tagging and attribute annotation tools. CVAT has semi-automated and automated labelling features: interactors (e.g., Segment Anything Model), detectors (e.g., YOLO v5), trackers (e.g. TransT - Transformer Tracking).

CVAT can be deployed as a tool on the AI4EOSC marketplace. For using CVAT, it is mandatory to have a storage provider linked (e.g. AI4EOSC Nextcloud). This is because, each time a user deletes a CVAT instance a snapshot will automatically be created in her/his storage. When a user deploys a new CVAT instance, she/he can either start from an existing snapshot or from a blank state (no snapshot).

2.6 - AI PROJECT TEMPLATES

AI project templates of the AI4EOSC ecosystem are structured and ready-to-use starting points boosting the development of new AI modules and projects within the platform. They help developers quickly set up projects that comply with the AI4EOSC integration requirements and best practices, and have reasonably standardised structure. The templates are based on cookiecutters and also offered through the AI4EOSC Templates web service⁸.

2.7 - DEEPaaS API

The DEEPaaS API (DEEP as a Service) is a REST API designed to provide simple, standardized access to machine learning and deep learning models. Built upon the

⁷ <https://www.cvat.ai/>

⁸ <https://templates.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/>

OpenAPI specification, it enables every AI/ML/DL module to be used as part of more complex services. The DEEPaaS API's primary goal is to make AI models easily accessible to users, supporting both inference and training operations. With the integrated Swagger interface, users can interact directly with underlying models, conveniently initiating model training or running inference tasks through a unified, user-friendly web interface.

2.8 - TRAINING PLATFORM

The training platform is an integrated, user-friendly environment built to support all stages of developing, training, and deploying AI models supporting the whole machine learning lifecycle. Registered users have the option of creating a new deployment, either from scratch or by selecting a module available on the marketplace. Within the general configuration of a deployment, users are required to choose between the Jupyter or VSCode IDE, specify the hardware configuration, provide the Docker tag and optionally provide credentials to mount the Nextcloud user directory. This deployment allows users to develop and train models with the resources available to them. These deployments are accessible by selecting the deployments on the platform.

2.9 - BATCH MODE

In batch mode a temporary job is created and is automatically terminated after training is done, allowing optimal resource allocation. The status of currently running and recent batch jobs can be viewed on the dashboard. It can be configured in a similar way as the standard mode but with the mandatory condition of linking a storage.

2.10 - JENKINS CI/CD

Jenkins⁹ is an open-source automation server used to implement CI/CD pipelines (Continuous Integration / Continuous Development) for all software components, including user applications. The pipeline automatically performs a series of actions for users each time users commit a change to their code. This ensures that all information and all builds throughout the project are tested and up to date with users' code. It ensures fast, reliable updates to live applications with minimal manual intervention.

2.11 - MLFLOW - EXPERIMENT TRACKING AND MODEL REGISTRY

MLflow ([MLflow, 2025](https://mlflow.org/)) is actively used on the AI4EOSC platform to support machine learning experiment tracking, model versioning, and artifact management across various ML frameworks. The deployment¹⁰ in production enables users to log parameters, metrics, and models, with over 20 experiments and 200+ active runs recorded to date. A self-registration interface allows researchers to join using their organisation credentials and manage access to shared experiments and registered models.

Through Vault-based secrets management, MLflow tracking credentials (i.e., MLflow tracking server endpoint, username and password) are automatically injected as environment variables when users launch a new deployment via Jupyter Notebooks or

⁹ <https://www.jenkins.io/>

¹⁰ <https://mlflow.cloud.ai4eosc.eu>

VSCoDe.

To support provenance tracking, a dedicated MLflow agent has been introduced with automatic *read permissions* across all experiments and registered models. The service is regularly maintained and has recently been upgraded to the latest MLflow version.

The advanced information on MLflow specific commands is documented in the platform documentation ([AI4OSdocs, 2025](#)): “How-to’s” -> “Use MLFlow for tracking your trainings” section¹¹.

2.12 - FEDERATED LEARNING SERVERS

Federated Learning (FL) is a paradigm enabling the collaborative training of a machine/deep learning model on decentralized systems, without the need of sharing the training data between the participants. It can be seen as a particular architecture of distributed learning especially useful for sensitive data, as it allows to train a global model without data centralization.

Within the AI4EOSC platform, users can perform a FL training either using NVIDIA's Federated Learning Application Runtime Environment (NVFLARE¹²) or Flower¹³ Federated AI Framework. Both frameworks can be used to deploy a FL server allowing the user to connect multiple clients from different AI4EOSC deployments, local machines or external cloud providers, enabling collaborative training.

The AI4EOSC dashboard offers multiple deployment options for the FL server. From the technical side, the users are able to adjust the number of CPUs and the amount of RAM and Disk storage according to their needs. In the case of the NVFlare FL server, users can access the NVFlare dashboard and retrieve the startup kit containing the essential configuration files, security certificates, and authentication credentials required to establish secure connections between the federated learning server on the AI4EOSC dashboard, clients, and admin users. Once the admins start the clients using retrieved startup kits, they can proceed to submit federated learning training jobs. For the case of the Flower FL server, users can configure it directly from the dashboard, detailing the number of clients, the aggregation strategy to be used, the aggregated metric for monitoring the performance of the training and even selecting additional privacy enhancing technologies and the tracking of the carbon footprint.

2.13 - PROVENANCE

Tracing the provenance of an AI module is essential to uphold the FAIR principles, ensuring reproducibility and trust in the module's predictions. It ensures transparency, trust, and reproducibility throughout the entire machine learning lifecycle. All provenance data is accessible through the platform, allowing users to verify, reproduce, or audit scientific work at any time. Each time a module's CI/CD pipeline runs, a provenance chain is generated by collecting information from various platform components based on the module's metadata. This data is compiled into a single RDF file that includes:

¹¹ <https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/howtos/develop/mlflow.html>

¹² <https://nvflare.readthedocs.io/en/main/>

¹³ <https://flower.ai/docs/>

- Build details from Jenkins (e.g., code tests, Docker image hashes),
- Training resource usage from Nomad,
- Experiment logs such as hyperparameters from MLflow,
- Module metadata like keywords, links, and timestamps.

The RDF file also maps how these components relate—for example, linking training datasets to deployments or Docker images to builds. To enhance usability, this provenance data is presented to users as an interactive, simplified graph, giving a clear overview of the module’s development and training history. Moreover, the user can ask LLM about the provenance graph, for example ask how the model is trained.

Figure 2.2: Example of the provenance graph for demo module on the Marketplace.

2.14 - DRIFT DETECTION & DRIFT MONITORING

Besides the Frouros¹⁴ as an open-source python package for drift detection in machine learning systems that allows performing both concept and data drift detection tasks, a new monitoring service called DriftWatch¹⁵ has been developed to visualise through a GUI the drifts detected over time.

This is designed as a framework-agnostic, open-source service optimized for drift detection reports, it allows users to monitor their data without committing to any specific provider. The use of tags enables users to work with any type of drift data, analysis, or method, ensuring adaptability to a wide range of use cases. Secured with OpenID Connect (OIDC), the authentication provides compatibility with federated authentication and fine-grained access control for groups, scopes and claims. A comprehensive API documented with OpenAPI 3.1, facilitates integration with external

¹⁴ <https://frouros.readthedocs.io/>

¹⁵ <https://drift-watch.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/>

systems, committing the service's flexibility and security. Additionally users can download a python client package that permits easy and direct report uploads within scripts and pipelines ([Esteban Sanchs B. et al, 2025](#)).

Figure 2.3: DriftWatch experiment drifts tracking and visualisation

As shown in [Figure 2.3](#), drift metrics are logged via the DriftWatch API, enabling real-time tracking and visualization of drift events in the dashboard. A use case that detects when the underwater camera becomes dirty has been implemented to showcase this service. More detailed information the reader can find here¹⁶.

¹⁶ <https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/drift-watch/howtos/develop/drift-watch.html#>

2.15 - AI4COMPOSE

AI4Compose is the component of the AI4EOSC platform that enables users to build composite AI workflows by combining multiple inference services into a single, orchestrated pipeline. Its main goal is to lower the technical barriers for creating and experimenting with complex AI workflows, while ensuring reproducibility, scalability, and accessibility—key principles of the AI4EOSC project. This is done with two complementary visual programming environments: Elyra (based on Jupyter Notebooks) and Node-RED (provided via the FlowFuse instance of the project¹⁷). Both tools rely on the actual execution of the inference in the AI4OS inference platform provided by OSCAR, as explained next.

2.16 - INFERENCE WITH OSCAR

The scalable inference of AI models is performed by the AI4OS inference platform, which is based on the open-source serverless platform OSCAR. OSCAR¹⁸ is built on Kubernetes for event-driven data-processing applications packaged as Docker containers.

The AI4OS inference platform¹⁹ consists of a pre-deployed production instance of the OSCAR cluster that is exclusively accessible to users belonging to the virtual organisation AI4EOSC (vo.ai4eosc.eu).

Users can access the OSCAR cluster via several methods that support EGI Check-in and AI4EOSC AAI (Keycloak):

- A web-based user interface.
- A command line interface (CLI).
- Through the oscar-python library.

It is also possible to deploy the OSCAR platform on any other public, on-premises or federated Cloud using the Infrastructure Manager (IM).

2.17 - INFRASTRUCTURE MANAGER²⁰

The Infrastructure Manager is a tool designed to simplify the access and usability of Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) clouds for scientific applications and AI workloads. It enables users to automatically deploy complex applications defined in the TOSCA standard, including AI models and related services, onto cloud infrastructures. The tool automates the selection, deployment, configuration, monitoring, and update of virtual appliances. Supporting APIs from various cloud platforms, it provides a contextualisation system for installing and configuring user-required applications. Users have multiple access methods, including a web-based GUI, an XML-RPC API, a REST API, and a command-line application.

¹⁷ <https://forge.flows.dev.ai4eosc.eu/>

¹⁸ <https://oscar.grycap.net/>

¹⁹ <https://dashboard.oscar.grycap.net/>

²⁰ <https://im.egi.eu/im-dashboard/login>

2.18 - AI4OS DOCUMENTATION²¹

AI4OS is the generic software stack powering deployments on various platforms such as AI4EOSC and iImagine. Comprehensive documentation for using this software and the associated platforms is available, providing users with a quickstart guide alongside detailed explanations on how to train or develop models and use the available tools. The documentation offers introductions, step-by-step tutorials for common tasks, and detailed information about modules and the user interface. Additionally, it provides an overview of key platform components, including the dashboard, authentication, data storage resources, the inference platform (OSCAR), the MLflow tracking server, and more. This resource serves as a complete guide to help users effectively navigate and utilize the AI4OS-powered platforms for their machine learning workflows.

2.19 - AI4EOSC LLM

AI4EOSC LLM is a Large Language Model chatbot service integrated into the AI4EOSC platform. It is able to summarize information, generate code recommendations or answer questions based on the documentation of the AI4EOSC dashboard. One important notice is that the chat history will be erased when the user will delete the deployment of the model, no data being retained by the platform.

2.20 - USER SUPPORT

Users of the AI4EOSC platform are supported through multiple ways: There is a dedicated ai4eosc-support email list and a web-page for Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ²²) that addresses common issues. The AI4OS Assistant, which is a LLM that uses the AI4EOSC documentation as a Knowledge Base to offer grounded responses to user questions. A status page is providing the information whether a particular service might be down. Newly added there is now also a AI4EOSC Helpdesk²³ using Zammad software²⁴ allowing users to raise tickets in a secure and private way and the AI4EOSC community forum²⁵ for more general discussions.

3. - INTEGRATION OF FINAL APPLICATIONS

The developed services are validated in practice and aligned with the needs of scientific communities. Three use cases started from the beginning of the project and four more were selected via open-calls in the final year of the project. Their progress and achieved results are reported in the following subsections.

3.1 - UC1-AGROMETEOROLOGY

The agrometeorology use case applies radar observations and AI methods to provide farmers with timely, localized warnings of high-impact weather events, particularly

²¹ <https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/>

²² <https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/help/faq.html>

²³ <https://helpdesk.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/>

²⁴ <https://zammad.com/en>

²⁵ <https://community.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/>

thunderstorms. Such events can endanger humans and animals, damage equipment and buildings, and reduce crop yields through hail and strong winds. Current general forecasts lack the spatial and temporal precision required for effective on-farm decisions, so this system aims to deliver nowcasting with ~30-minute lead time, allowing farmers to protect people, assets, and crops. By leveraging radar data coverage and AI models that capture non-linear natural processes, the system generates accurate, actionable predictions, supporting farm resilience and sustainable practices. Expected impact: reduced weather-related losses, improved safety, smarter operations, and potential scalability across the EU.

3.1.1 - Achieved results

Data curation

The data come from radar of the manufacturer MicroStep-MIS (type MMR-116²⁶, see [Figure UC1.1](#)). It is an X-band radar, working with a signal wavelength of 3.19 cm, and producing full volume scans with a frequency of about 5–5.5 minutes. The standard range of the radar is over 150 km.

Figure UC1.1: MMR-116 Radar placed on a building roof.

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https://www.microstep-mis.com/web/products?category=meteorology_climatology&product=mr-116_mini_meteorological_radar

The radar has been working in a continuous regime since the year 2015. Due to magnetron issues in early 2015, only data from 2016–2020 were used. The analysis was further limited to April–September, when thunderstorms are most likely.

From the radar volume scans, the Pseudo CAPPI 2000 data were retrieved. CAPPI (Constant Altitude Plan Position Indicator) is a standard and widely used radar product, based on a number of Plan Position Indicator (PPI) scans, which is the most elemental product. Data available from one elevation (one rotation of radar) are lately displayed on the surface of the ground. The number of elevation can be specified as a parameter. The process of generation is based on the bilinear interpolation for every point of the picture from two nearest shots of the elevation. X-axis in the final picture represents longitude and latitude. The position of the radar is in the centre of the picture (see [Figure UC1.2](#)).

Figure UC1.2: CAPPI product for the altitude of 2000 m; 2020-01-23, 21:15 UTC.

CAPPI is obtained by interpolating PPI scans to a horizontal slice at constant height. In Pseudo CAPPI, reflectivity from the lowest available PPI is used where no direct intersection exists. The 2000 m level was chosen as it corresponds to key convective processes; henceforth, we refer to it simply as CAPPI.

Vertically Integrated Liquid (VIL) is the total amount of rain that would fall if all the liquid water in a column within a rain cloud (usually a thunderstorm) reached the surface of the earth. Basically, all water quantities estimated on the basis of reflectivity are added over a grid-like distributed unit of area. VIL is not observed or measured, but calculated based on the reflectivity measured by the radar. Note that meteorologically

relevant events are extremely rare by their nature as can be illustrated by the [Table UC1.1](#), showing the ratio of NaN values (e.g. no reflectivity = clear sky) to the total number of measurements for the individual administrative areas for both CAPPI and VIL.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
CAPPI	81%	77%	80%	86%	90%	90%	83%	85%	86%	86%	88%	81%	82%
VIL	56%	9%	9%	64%	16%	88%	56%	51%	83%	70%	22%	75%	18%

Table UC1.1: Ratio of NaN values to the total number of measurements for areas.

The [Table UC1.1](#) also demonstrates an interesting phenomena: Areas 2, 3, 5, 11 and 13 are affected by the background radar noise, which is indicated by significantly lower NaN ratios for VIL for these areas.

Figure UC1.3: Radar coverage of the investigated region. Green color denotes the reach of the radar signal.

Additionally, during the preliminary data analysis, we have discovered that part of the radar signal is blocked by mountains as is shown in [Figure UC1.3](#).

In the current work, however, we did not work with the CAPPI values directly. Instead, we converted them into a system of qualitative classification (see [Table UC1.2](#)) utilizing warning levels, which subsequently can be converted to binary “warning classes”, where ‘0’ yields no convective event, and ‘1’ indicates intense convective events, in line with the generally accepted approach of the units of crisis management where warnings on different meteorological, hydrological or other phenomena are expressed in terms of numerical codes and are also visualized by different colors.

dBZ	<0,43.5)	44	44,5	...	59	59.5	<60,∞)
Levels	0	1	2	...	28	29	30

Table UC1.2: Intermediate conversion of dBZ values to warning levels.

CAPPI values were first converted into warning levels (multi-class categories, see [Table UC1.2](#)) for each radar pixel within each radar measurement. These levels correspond to different intensity thresholds of convective activity. For later analysis, we aggregated these warning levels into a binary warning class (0 = no convective event, 1 = intense convective event). For each area, the class was derived from radar pixels using the average of the two highest warning level values, rounded up. Multiple threshold levels were tested.

This preprocessing has been carried out internally using MicroStep-MIS’ resources. We have used the NextCloud storage provided by the AI4EOSC platform, to store our data. During the data preprocessing phase drift monitoring was carried out using the Frouros library. The data will be shared with the research community based on request.

In addition, we have also purchased station point precipitation data from Czech Hydro metrological Institute covering the radar area from years 2016 - 2020, the total number of stations was 37. The frequency of precipitation data was 10 minutes. The preliminary experiments with inclusion of these data didn’t bring additional improvements to the models based solely on radar data.

Model validation

Designing effective deep learning (DL) models for radar-based precipitation nowcasting presents multiple interrelated challenges. One of the most fundamental issues lies in the specific nature of the dataset. Thunderstorm datasets—especially those derived from radar reflectivity—tend to be highly imbalanced. High-impact weather events such as intense convective cells are rare compared to the prevalence of low or moderate precipitation. However, these rare events are often the most important for end users, such as meteorologists and farmers. Therefore, it is essential to balance the representation of significant events (e.g., reflectivity above 46–50 dBZ) against the need for a large and diverse training set that covers typical meteorological conditions. This balance ensures that the model doesn't become biased toward underpredicting

extreme events. In this context it makes sense to develop several nowcasting models with respect to the “extreme thunderstorm” cutoff. After multiple discussions with meteorologists, we have decided to further investigate boundaries ranging from 47,5 to 52 dBZ in 0.5 dBZ steps as shown in [Table UC1.2](#). These and other boundaries of interest can be specified via the `threshold_value` (parameter to specify the cutoff between extreme and moderate thunderstorms, which is based on [Table UC1.2](#) and thus can be specified in 0.5 dBZ steps. Furthermore, the issue of different lead times adds another layer of complexity. As the forecast horizon increases (e.g., from 5 to 60 minutes), the quality of the predictions typically deteriorates. This degradation is often nonlinear, with sharp declines in skill after 20–30 minutes. Capturing this dynamic requires careful model design and performance monitoring that explicitly accounts for the lead time dimension. We have therefore decided to limit the lead times to a maximum of 40 minutes and to develop 8 independent models for each lead time. This and other parameters can be set via configurations²⁷.

Validation. We have validated the developed models’ performance by calculating the metrics such as probability of detection (POD), false alarm ratio (FAR), critical success index (CSI), F1 score and/or other scores in order to document the improvement of the new model compared to state-of-the-art techniques in predicting thunderstorm situations. Meteorologists typically use POD, FAR and CSI metrics to quantify the performance of different models, as illustrated in [Figure UC1.4](#).

Figure UC1.4: A schematic to illustrate the definition of the metrics of success. ‘A’ denotes hits (true positives), ‘B’ is for misses (false negatives), and ‘C’ stands for false alarms (false positives).

The aforementioned metrics of success are defined on the basis of contingency tables, which contain the conditional frequency distributions of the occurrence of the possible events of a statistical experiment.

In the simplest case of nowcasting, a binary classification into two categories is evaluated: 0 (Negatives) - no thunderstorm and 1 (Positives) - thunderstorm occurrence. At each point in time, each pixel is classified as either 0 or 1. This result is compared to the predicted values of 0 or 1. A summation over all pixels results in a 2x2 contingency table for a given point in time, as schematically shown in [Table UC1.3](#)

²⁷ Configurations and parameters can be found here:

https://github.com/ai4os-hub/thunderstorm-nowcast-microstep/tree/main/data/configs/config_data_management

For time t	Observed 0	Observed 1
Forecast 0	True negatives (TN) – correctly identified no-thunderstorm events	False negatives (FN) – wrongly labeled thunderstorm events
Forecast 1	False positives (FP) – wrongly labeled no-thunderstorm events	True positives (TP) – correctly identified thunderstorm events

Table UC1.3: Contingency table for two categories of events.

In the next step, one sums the values in each cell of the contingency table over all points in time during the examined period. This will provide the summary data for metrics to obtain an overview about the performance of the analysed nowcasting model averaged both over time and space.

The results of our experiments are presented in Figures [UC1.5 \(a\)](#) and [UC1.5 \(b\)](#) which contain 8 lead times x 5 thresholds = 40 different models.

Figure UC1.5 (a): Performance of models with different thresholds and lead times.

Figure UC1.5 (b): Performance of models with different thresholds and lead times.

Case-studies. In addition to statistical validation, several cases of nowcasting performance were evaluated manually by meteorologists, to gain better insight into individual situations; one such example is illustrated in [Figure UC1.6](#). Meteorologists found the visual warning product prototype intuitive and easy to interpret. They expressed interest in adding XAI explanations to improve transparency and trust. Overall, they are cautiously optimistic about the model's performance, while emphasising the need for more thorough evaluation before operational use.

Implementation considerations. The programming part of the modelling process was greatly simplified by utilizing the AI4EOSC template, which combined the advantages of the data science cookiecutter template and integration with DEEPaS. Jenkins pipelines containing code quality check, automatic Docker Image building and updates to the Marketplace simplified the MLOps aspects of modeling. We have heavily relied on MLflow for model versioning and experiment tracking.

In the course of the project, we, in collaboration with project partners, have also investigated possibilities for training nowcasting models on geographically partitioned radar data without requiring data centralization. The proposed method, adaptFL, was published in ([Sáinz-Pardo Díaz, J. et al, 2024](#)), that highlights promising directions for addressing geographic heterogeneity and data locality in radar-based nowcasting. In the study, a radar domain of 400 km was divided into four clients, each trained on local data with shared updates. Our paper shows that adaptFL significantly outperforms baseline models trained either independently or via standard federated averaging by adapting to local data distributions while still leveraging knowledge from other domains.

Service delivery

The developed model (actually 8 of them – one for each forecasted lead time) is deployed in the OSCAR cluster and it works in the following manner:

1. Input data are transferred from Forecasting virtual machine to the MinIO object storage²⁸ system used by the OSCAR inference platform.
2. This automatically triggers the inference execution of the model, using an asynchronous OSCAR service invocation. The output prediction is stored in a MinIO bucket.
3. The output data are transferred back to Forecasting virtual machine, where they serve as an input to the geoserver to show warnings using simple 3 color (semaphor) scheme to be easily understandable for farmers and trigger a notification e-mail service if warranted.

²⁸ <https://www.min.io/>

Figure UC1.6: An example of a cold front movement (2022-07-01).

This pipeline – from radar data collection to ML deployment and issue of warning alerts – forms a replicable and scalable pattern that can be reused to develop additional nowcasting models in the future. The current pilot demonstrates the feasibility and impact of this approach.

3.1.2 - Findings and Outlook

The thunderstorm nowcasting application was developed on the AI4EOsc platform, using its cloud infrastructure to train, evaluate, and deploy a deep learning model for short-term severe weather prediction. In the course of the project we were able to complete all our User stories defined in D6.1 (Berberi et al., 2023). The platform offered key services such as JupyterLab for development, cloud-based training and inference (UC1.E01.US01 “Provisioning Computing resources”, UC1.E01.US04 “Able to experiment with different AI techniques”), workflow orchestration via Jenkins (UC01.E01.US02 “Performing Automated Testing”), and integrated data management and experiment tracking tools. MLflow supported reproducibility and experiment tracking (UC01.E01.US03 “Tracking and Comparing Experiments”), while OSCAR enabled deployment and operationalization.

Overall, the platform provided a solid and scalable foundation, despite some initial challenges with workflow customization and system integration. These were gradually resolved, allowing development to progress as planned.

Next steps will focus on refining the model to improve prediction accuracy, incorporating additional meteorological features, and optimizing performance for near-real-time use. To engage end-users, a user-friendly visualization interface will be developed in collaboration with meteorologists, ensuring the system delivers both scientific and operational value.

3.2 - UC2-PLANT PROTECTION

The Plant Protection use case focuses on the early detection of crop diseases using a combination of visual symptoms, phenological data, and expert annotation. The goal is to build robust machine learning models that can identify signs of disease before they cause significant yield loss, enabling timely and targeted plant protection measures.

This approach integrates existing advisory workflows with AI-driven tools, leveraging domain expertise, mobile data collection, and cloud-based processing. It also aims to democratize access to plant disease diagnostics, making it available not only to experts, but also to farmers with limited agronomic knowledge.

3.1.1 - Achieved results

Data curation

A dedicated data acquisition and annotation workflow was implemented to support machine learning development for plant disease detection. The national agricultural advisory system (eDWIN - eODR²⁹) was extended with new configuration settings and API endpoints that trigger a custom mobile form. This form allows field advisors to submit standardized disease monitoring reports, including up to six images per observation and labels describing whether the plants are healthy or infected. Example images originating from reports submitted by advisors during field monitoring – illustrating *Cercospora* leaf spot on sugar beet and brown rust on rye – are presented in Figures [UC2.1](#) and [UC2.2](#), respectively.

²⁹ <https://www.edwin.gov.pl/> , <https://edwin.eodr.pl/>

Figure UC2.1: Sugar beet leaf (*Beta vulgaris*) displaying visible symptoms of *Cercospora* leaf spot (*Cercospora beticola*), one of the most serious foliar diseases affecting this crop.

Figure. UC2.2: Rye leaf (*Secale cereale*) with clear symptoms of brown rust (*Puccinia striiformis*), a fungal disease of cereal crops. The characteristic linear brown-orange pustules are visible along the leaf veins, indicating an active infection.

Data collection is carried out by trained advisors and researchers from the Institute of Plant Protection, ensuring domain-specific accuracy. Each report submitted by an advisor is routed to a supervisor (coordinator) through a dedicated module allowing for expert verification and correction. Verified datasets – comprising both images and structured metadata – are then transferred to the IBIS server³⁰, where they are securely stored in a dedicated schema optimized for ML ingestion and processing. An example JSON structure of a report is presented in [Figure UC2.3](#).

```
{
  "diseaseParameters": {
    "percentageDamageOfArea": 0
  },
  "bbchStage": {
    "stageCode": "14",
    "stageId": "511",
    "stageName": "Faza 4 liści (2 pary)"
  },
  "archived": false,
  "userType": "OBSERVER",
  "bbchStageList": [],
  "diseaseId": "29",
  "intervention": false,
  "monitoringType": "1",
  "notes": "",
  "plantId": "4",
  "pointId": "3352",
  "reportDate": "2024-07-19T12:56:27.827Z",
  "type": "DISEASE",
  "user": "16393",
  "public": true,
  "valid": "CONFIRMED",
  "ai4eosc": "APPROVED",
  "ai4eoscPhotos": [
    "https://beta.ibis.apps.psn.pl/ai4eosc/resources/beet_unaffected_early_july/images/d3e194e3-de71-4fdc-9299-b2873be7c09c.jpg",
    "https://beta.ibis.apps.psn.pl/ai4eosc/resources/beet_unaffected_early_july/images/a5d96dce-03b5-44e2-8b61-04430498fb5c.jpg",
    "https://beta.ibis.apps.psn.pl/ai4eosc/resources/beet_unaffected_early_july/images/7223cb72-7c60-4ec8-afaa-c612e8176fc5.jpg",
    "https://beta.ibis.apps.psn.pl/ai4eosc/resources/beet_unaffected_early_july/images/69377dd7-8919-4b23-b2d8-37385ac241c2.jpg",
    "https://beta.ibis.apps.psn.pl/ai4eosc/resources/beet_unaffected_early_july/images/5a490721-3816-413d-8cba-a0f421fe1f1f.jpg",
    "https://beta.ibis.apps.psn.pl/ai4eosc/resources/beet_unaffected_early_july/images/56400e4c-120b-46e8-a12d-037bd4fd8276.jpg"
  ],
  "createdAt": "2024-07-19T11:08:48.000Z",
  "updatedAt": "2024-07-19T11:08:48.000Z",
  "id": "669a4940311e8e9e9804fcd6",
  "photos": [
    {
      "name": "56400e4c-120b-46e8-a12d-037bd4fd8276.jpg",
      "url": "https://ibis.apps.psn.pl/tenants/edwin-demo/api/spaces/reports/packages/issue/669a4940311e8e9e9804fcd6/only/files/56400e4c-120b-46e8-a12d-037bd4fd8276.jpg",
      "category": "healthy"
    },
    {
      "name": "5a490721-3816-413d-8cba-a0f421fe1f1f.jpg",
      "url": "https://ibis.apps.psn.pl/tenants/edwin-demo/api/spaces/reports/packages/issue/669a4940311e8e9e9804fcd6/only/files/5a490721-3816-413d-8cba-a0f421fe1f1f.jpg",
      "category": "healthy"
    },
    {
      "name": "69377dd7-8919-4b23-b2d8-37385ac241c2.jpg",
      "url": "https://ibis.apps.psn.pl/tenants/edwin-demo/api/spaces/reports/packages/issue/669a4940311e8e9e9804fcd6/only/files/69377dd7-8919-4b23-b2d8-37385ac241c2.jpg",
      "category": "healthy"
    },
    {
      "name": "7223cb72-7c60-4ec8-afaa-c612e8176fc5.jpg",
      "url": "https://ibis.apps.psn.pl/tenants/edwin-demo/api/spaces/reports/packages/issue/669a4940311e8e9e9804fcd6/only/files/7223cb72-7c60-4ec8-afaa-c612e8176fc5.jpg",
      "category": "healthy"
    },
    {
      "name": "a5d96dce-03b5-44e2-8b61-04430498fb5c.jpg",
      "url": "https://ibis.apps.psn.pl/tenants/edwin-demo/api/spaces/reports/packages/issue/669a4940311e8e9e9804fcd6/only/files/a5d96dce-03b5-44e2-8b61-04430498fb5c.jpg",
      "category": "healthy"
    },
    {
      "name": "d3e194e3-de71-4fdc-9299-b2873be7c09c.jpg",
      "url": "https://ibis.apps.psn.pl/tenants/edwin-demo/api/spaces/reports/packages/issue/669a4940311e8e9e9804fcd6/only/files/d3e194e3-de71-4fdc-9299-b2873be7c09c.jpg",
      "category": "healthy"
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure UC2.3: JSON structure of the report sent by the expert via a dedicated mobile application. The report contains additional information about the photo and flags allowing it to be categorized as a report for machine learning.

AI models training

Current recognition methods use deep learning models. We focused on creating a solution resistant to hallucination. Therefore we decided to build a deep learning system composed of two Convolutional neural network models.

³⁰ <https://beta.ibis.apps.psn.pl/ai4eosc/>

Convolutional neural networks, or CNNs, are a type of artificial intelligence model designed to “see” and understand images, much like the human visual system. You can think of them as a system of layered filters that gradually learn to detect increasingly complex features in a picture.

At the beginning, the model looks at very basic patterns—edges, lines, or simple shapes. As the image passes through deeper layers, the network starts recognizing more detailed elements, such as parts of a leaf, disease spots, or texture changes. Eventually, the network can associate these features with specific conditions like a healthy plant or a fungal infection.

The power of CNNs lies in their ability to **automatically learn what to look for**, without us explicitly telling them which features matter. Instead of hardcoding rules like “brown spots mean Cercospora,” we show the network enough examples, and it figures that out on its own. This makes CNNs ideal for problems where visual patterns are complex or subtle—like identifying early stages of plant disease.

- The task of the first model is semantic segmentation. We implemented the U-Net architecture model.
- We use the obtained model to extract the main area indicating the leaves class. Leaves clearly inform the classifier about the health of plants. We ensure that background artifacts, soil, weeds will not affect the next model's predictions, which will be focused on disease occurrence.
- The second task is classification. We implemented the CNN model for binary classification.
- Input to models are 512x512 RGB images. During training we used data augmentation and undersampling. Pytorch was used to build the system, implement and train models.

The dataset used for the training has been published on Zenodo ([Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center, 2025](#)) and it contains high-resolution RGB images captured by PSNC and WODR for the dataset specifically designed for training two models to recognize Cercospora Leaf in beet and Brown Rust of Rye in rye. The dataset has been utilized to train CNN models for the AI module available at AI4EOSC marketplace that are integrated into the mobile application of eDWIN advisory platform.

Rye - resnet34:

accuracy: 0.983713

- Predictions³¹
- Deployment³²

Beet - resnet101:

val accuracy: 0.938202

- Predictions³³
- Deployment³⁴

Integrated Plant Protection module

The module contains 2 fine-tuned models³⁵. A fine-tuning pipeline is implemented in [PyTorch](#). Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) serve as the backbone architecture for classifiers.

For rye images, a pretrained [ResNet-34](#) model was used and named [rye-34](#). For beet images, a pretrained [ResNet-101](#) model was used and named [beet-101](#).

Images are preprocessed with normalization and resizing to 256x256 before being fed to the models. For data augmentation, training images are randomly cropped and flipped horizontally. The output layer of each classifier is adjusted to the number of classes. We have [brown_rust](#), [unaffected](#) classes for rye and [cercospora](#), and [unaffected](#) classes for beet. The result of the model consists of tensors of shape (batch_size, num_classes) containing the predicted classes' logits. The API returns the predicted class with the highest logit value for each input image along with the corresponding probability of the predicted class.

Cross-entropy loss is the objective function used to guide model training in classification tasks. An SGD optimizer with momentum is used to update the model weights. A learning rate scheduler reduces the learning rate by a factor of 0.1 every 7 epochs. The training process lasts for 20 epochs per model.

Model validation

Machine learning experts from the project use these high-quality datasets to train disease detection models. The first models were focused on *Secale cereale* (rye) and *Beta vulgaris* (sugar beet), specifically targeting brown rust and Cercospora leaf spot.

³¹

https://beta.ibis.apps.psnk.pl/ai4eosc/models/ibis-deployment-ai4eosc-img-classification-rye/2025-07-13_18-46-27/

³²

https://beta.ibis.apps.psnk.pl/ai4eosc/models/ibis-deployment-ai4eosc-img-classification-rye/2025-07-13_18-46-27/

³³

https://beta.ibis.apps.psnk.pl/ai4eosc/models/ibis-deployment-ai4eosc-img-classification-beet/2025-07-13_20-11-05/

³⁴

https://beta.ibis.apps.psnk.pl/ai4eosc/models/ibis-deployment-ai4eosc-img-classification-beet/2025-07-13_20-11-05/

³⁵ <https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/catalog/modules/integrated-plant-protection>

What distinguishes this use case is the incorporation of **expert-in-the-loop validation**: trained advisors can directly test the preliminary models within the mobile application they already use for agrophage³⁶ monitoring. The app displays the model's prediction, which the advisor can confirm or correct. This allows for fine-grained feedback and iterative model improvement based on real-world usage by domain experts. The ongoing evaluation process ensures that the model achieves high precision before being moved to broader deployment.

Service delivery

Once validated, the final models will be deployed in the production environment of the **Virtual Farm** application – a platform made available to farmers. There, farmers will be able to use their smartphone cameras to detect plant diseases, even without expert-level knowledge.

This pipeline – from field data collection to ML deployment – forms a replicable and scalable pattern that can be reused to develop additional disease models in the future.

Availability of the “Integrated plant protection” application on the AI4EOSC marketplace allows other researchers to assess it via Docker image download or 10-min “try” deployment.

The current pilot demonstrates the feasibility and impact of this approach and will be expanded with more crops and disease targets as part of the broader AI4EOSC roadmap.

3.1.2 - Findings and Outlook

AI4EOSC project helped us to successfully develop our use case and complete User stories defined in D6.1 ([Berberi et al., 2023](#)) with three Epics “Input data management”, “Building and Deploying a ML Model/System”, and “End user service for agrophages recognition”.

Improvements plan

The current implementation within the AI4EOSC project has successfully demonstrated the feasibility of deploying AI models for early disease detection in crops, with two pilot models already integrated into the advisory system. These initial results confirm the potential of AI-assisted diagnostics in real-world agricultural settings.

Looking ahead, the goal is to significantly expand the scope of this approach by training and deploying models for a broader range of plant diseases and pests. By building on the existing framework, we aim to transform the system into a comprehensive decision-support tool. Once scaled, farmers will be able to use their

³⁶ *Agrophage* (from Greek *agros* – field, and *phagein* – to eat) refers to any organism that feeds on or damages cultivated plants, including pests (insects, mites), pathogens (fungi, bacteria, viruses), and parasitic weeds. In agricultural science, the term is commonly used to describe biological threats to crop production.

smartphones to identify pests and diseases directly in the field – without the need for immediate consultation with an advisor.

Based on the recognition results, the system will also be able to automatically generate recommendations for plant protection measures, suggesting specific active substances appropriate for combating the identified disease or pest. This functionality will further increase the practical value of the tool, enabling faster and more precise responses in the field.

User engagements

While the eDWIN platform places strong emphasis on the dissemination of pest and disease occurrence data, user engagement – particularly among farmers – remains a key challenge. Field advisors across Poland actively contribute to the system by reporting numerous local agrophage incidents. However, only a limited number of farmers currently take full advantage of the alerts and recommendations generated from these observations.

The addition of AI-based diagnostics to the monitoring process is expected to significantly enhance the value of the system. Experts confirm the platform performs reliably and provides actionable insights – the next step is to ensure that a broader audience of farmers recognizes and benefits from these capabilities.

To increase adoption, targeted promotional efforts are needed, including outreach at agricultural fairs, focused advertising campaigns, and community-based engagement. Encouraging satisfied users to share their positive experiences with peers will be essential in building trust and expanding the user base.

3.3 - UC3-AUTOMATED THERMOGRAPHY

Use case 3 is centred around thermography and how the technology can be leveraged to improve the efficiency of energy-related systems in the urban environment. By capturing so-called “heat images” of city scenes, thermal anomalies can be identified that correspond to areas of unwanted heat loss that require maintenance attention. The focus lies on heat provision to end-energy users - from supply (district heating) to the usage itself (buildings). The two applications are:

- I. Detecting thermal hotspots on building rooftops caused by thermal bridges. Urban planners and building owners can thereby be supported by identifying retrofitting potential.
- II. Detecting thermal hotspots caused by leaks from underground district heating system (DHS) pipelines. This is a two-fold implementation where thermal regions of interest are first identified and then various false alarms stemming from common urban features (cars, manholes, streetlamps, etc.) are sorted out. This application supports DHS operators in their search for pipeline leaks by providing a honed list of potential suspects.

At present, the inability to rapidly and accurately identify the described areas of unwanted heat loss hinders efforts to maintain high energy efficiency in urban infrastructure. To address this, the overarching goal is to automate the detection of thermal anomalies, thereby accelerating the implementation of necessary countermeasures and repairs. AI can support this objective either as a stand-alone tool (I) or through integration into existing analysis pipelines (II).

3.3.1 - Achieved results

This section discusses the results achieved during the course of the project to create, train, and make publicly available three models in total, associated with the two afore-mentioned application areas. These are:

- I) The “**Thermal Bridges on Building Rooftops Detector (TBRDet)**” ([Mayer et al., 2023a](#))
- II) The “**Thermal Anomaly Segmenter (TASeg)**” ([Vollmer et al., 2025b](#)) and “**Thermal Urban Feature Segmenter (TUFSeg)**” ([Vollmer et al., 2025a](#))

The following subsections describe the various aspects relevant for and associated with these implementations. The user stories defined at the beginning of the project in D6.1 ([Berberi et al., 2023](#)) hereby act as guidelines and the extent of their realisation is discussed in each appropriate chapter. As indicated by the associated references, additional details can be found in the journal publications. In total, the following peer-reviewed publications were generated in association with this use case over the course of the project: [Vollmer et al. \(2024b\)](#), [Vollmer et al. \(2025a\)](#), [Vollmer et al. \(2025b\)](#), and [Duda et al. \(2025a\)](#).

Data curation

As previously highlighted, the use case is focused on TIR (thermal infrared) imagery. A manner in which such data can be efficiently and effectively captured is via UASs (unmanned aircraft systems) – colloquially known as drones. The remote sensing aspect of this form of acquisition enables the access of areas unreachable via ground-based methods (hand-held or vehicle-mounted sensors), while allowing for larger ground sampling distances at lower cost than other aerial vehicles (airplanes, helicopters). The flight and image capture process can be automated so that the pilot is only required for landing. Additionally, the method is flexible and little time is needed to acquire permits given the nature of the flights (people are not recognisable).

To acquire the data for this use case, we collaborated with the Air Bavarian GmbH³⁷, a German UAS company based close to Munich. A Zenmuse XT2 dual camera with FLIR Tau 2 thermal and 4k RGB (red green blue) sensor was used, meaning both TIR and standard colour images were acquired simultaneously. The resolutions of these vary - 640x512 pixels for the TIRs, 4000x3000 pixels for the RGBs. A DJI Matrice 600 or 300 UAS was used to fly at a consistent flight height of 60 m above the ground. The

³⁷ <https://air-bavarian.com/>

following table details aspects pertaining to image acquisition. As both models from II. use the same data foundation, the table is not aggregated on model level.

	Application I)	Application II)
Location	Karlsruhe (DE)	Karlsruhe + Munich (DE)
Year	March, 2019	January and March, 2022 + December, 2019
Time	Morning (8 AM – 9 AM)	Nighttime (7 PM – 6 AM)
Ambient temperatures	4°C – 5°C	-5°C – 2°C
UAS pitch	45°	90° (nadir)
No. of flights	5	2 + 49
No. of images	~3000	~1500 + ~55000

Table UC3.1: Details of data acquisition

As [Table UC3.1](#) shows, some of these datasets were acquired before the project started, while additional ones were captured during the project to expand upon the regions of study. Through these acquisitions, a large data basis was created, thus fulfilling the initial part of UC3.E01.US01 “Storing and sharing the acquired raw images for long-term use”. The other key aspect of this - as well as UC3.E02.US01 “Collecting and storing thermal images” - is provided by the platform, specifically through NextCloud. The large capacity of this cloud-based storage option enabled the storage of all these datasets in their raw as well as processed form.

The next step, while not formalised as a separate user story, was key in generating the training dataset: Data processing. Here, the steps vary for each model as each has its particular task and therefore requires a specialised dataset. The following table details key aspects of the various approaches:

	Application I)	Application II)	
Model	TBBDet	TASeg	TUFSeg
Image type(s)	TIR + RGB	TIR	TIR + RGB // TIR
Additional information	-	DHS pipe locations	-
Channels	5-channel (R + G + B + T + Height)	3-channel (T + T + T)	4-channel (R + G + B + T)
Processing steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Remove distortion from RGBs 2. Create 3D model from RGBs 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Georeference TIRs 2. Mask TIRs with DHS pipe locations to create T_m 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Remove distortion from RGBs 2. Align RGBs

	Application I)	Application II)	
	3. Create height maps from 3D model 4. Align RGBs, TIRs and height maps 5. Stack to [R, G, B, T, H] For more details, see Mayer et al. (2023b) .	(masked temperature array) 3. Stack to [T _m , T _m , T _u] (unmasked temperature array) For more details, see Vollmer et al. (2025b) .	and TIRs 3. Stack to [R, G, B, T] For more details, see Vollmer et al. (2025a) .
Zenodo DOIs	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7022736 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7360996	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14287864	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814413

Table UC3.2: Details of model-specific data preprocessing

As one can tell from [Table UC3.2](#), the preprocessing steps for the three models vary considerably. The TASEg does not make use of the simultaneously acquired RGBs, as it aims to identify in particular those thermal anomalies stemming from leaks that cannot be seen in standard colour images. More relevant here is a means by which to focus the model on areas above and around the DHS, which is achieved by using the geographic pipeline information to mask the images and having these honed images form the basis of the data foundation ([Vollmer et al., 2025b](#)). The other two models make use of the colour images to provide additional context information. As the RGBs suffer from fish-eye distortion, they require correction before they can be registered to align with the TIRs ([Mayer et al., 2023b](#); [Vollmer et al., 2025a](#)). For the TBBRDet, which targets anomalies on rooftops, an additional step of generating height maps is included to focus the search to areas above the ground.

A summary of the resulting, processed datasets can be found in [Table UC3.3](#). Not only was NextCloud leveraged to store all these datasets again, but they were also all published to Zenodo and are part of the AI4EOSC community. Once part of a Zenodo community, they are available to all platform users and can be automatically loaded into development deployments, thus enabling future users to use these for their own models or the ones described in the following subsection.

Model	TBBRDet	TASEg	TUFSeg
Dataset size	926 stacked .npys (all from Karlsruhe)	3440 stacked .npys (900 from Karlsruhe, 2540 from Munich) Generated: 3171 Manual: 269	793 stacked .npys (93 from Karlsruhe, 700 from Munich)
Train set	731	Generated: 2142 Manual: 172	634
Validate set	-	Generated: 404 Manual: 53	-
Test set	195	Generated: 625	159

Model	TBBRDet	TASeg	TUFSeg
		Manual: 45	

Table UC3.3: Details of model-specific datasets

The last necessary step in preparing the datasets for supervised AI model training is the creation of annotations. This relates to user story UC3.E01.US02 “Labeling the image data” and was accomplished using *VIA (VGG Image Annotator)*³⁸, a software from the Visual Geometry Group³⁹. However, as can be gleaned from the rather small dataset sizes for the TBBRDet and TUFSeg models, this manual annotation process is cumbersome and time-consuming. For TASeg, a different approach was therefore implemented based on a two-part dataset, consisting of the so-called “generated” and “manual” dataset. Annotations for the much larger “generated” set were created automatically as the outputs of the best-performing traditional computer vision method for anomaly detection, namely triangle-histogram-thresholding (Vollmer et al., 2024b). A much smaller “manual” dataset was then used for fine-tuning, the creation of which required considerably less effort to generate. For more information on the developed procedure, see Vollmer et al. (2025b). The ground truth labels for supervised model training and evaluation, as described in Table UC3.4, are naturally also included in the Zenodo publications and therefore available to all users.

	Application I.	Application II.	
Model	TBBRDet	TASeg	TUFSeg
Type of analysis problem	Object detection / instance segmentation	Semantic segmentation	Semantic segmentation
Label types	Bounding boxes / segmentation masks	Segmentation masks	Segmentation masks
Classification task	Binary	Binary	Multiclass
Classes	Thermal bridge	Thermal anomaly, background	Building, car (cold), car (warm), manhole (cold), manhole (warm), miscellaneous, person, street lamp (cold), street lamp (warm), background

³⁸ https://www.robots.ox.ac.uk/~vqg/software/via/via_demo.html

³⁹ While the CVAT annotation tool has recently been integrated into the platform and is surely a great support for users with newer datasets, it was not yet available at the time when labelling was performed and therefore was not used.

	Application I.	Application II.	
Annotation amounts	6895 thermal bridge annotations	1 056 686 pixels of interest out of 927 989 760 total (= 0.11%) Generated dataset: 880 432 out of 785 448 960 total Manual dataset: 176 254 out of 142 540 800 total	11 060 523 pixels of interest out of 216 418 040 total (= 5.11%) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● background: 205 357 517, ● building: 4 811 126, ● car (cold): 3 804 713, ● car (warm): 1 993 912, ● manhole (cold): 92 415, ● manhole (warm): 244 538, ● miscellaneous: 50 762, ● person: 38 901, ● streetlamp (cold): 22 822, ● streetlamp (warm): 1 334

Table UC3.4: Details of analysis problem and annotations

Model development and validation

The datasets in the previous subsection were used extensively for the training of all manner of model architectures and variants. [Table UC3.5](#) summarises key aspects.

	Application I.	Application II.	
Model	TBBDet	TASeg	TUFSeg
Python	3.6	3.10	3.8
Framework	PyTorch 1.10.1	PyTorch 2.0.1	Tensorflow 2.10.0
Toolbox	<i>MMDetection</i> (Chen et al. 2019)	<i>transformers</i> (Wolf et al., 2020); <i>segmentation_models.pytorch</i> (Iakubovskii 2019b)	<i>segmentation_models</i> (Iakubovskii 2019a)
Architecture(s)	MaskRCNN Swin-T Transformer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SegFormer B0 - B4 ● DeepLabV3+ ResNet-101 ● U-Net ResNet-101 ● PSPNet ResNet-101 	U-Net ResNet-152 / MobileNetv2
Loss function(s)	Sigmoid cross entropy	Binary cross entropy (BCE), Dice, Jaccard, Tversky	Sigmoid focal cross entropy
Evaluation metrics	AR@1, AR@10, AR@100 (Recall averaged over a 0.5 - 0.95 IoU range for	Intersection over Union (IoU), F2-score, Recall (R), Precision (P)	Accuracy (A), balanced A, P, weighted P, IoU, weighted IoU, weighted

	Application I.	Application II.	
	the top 1 / 10 / 100 detections per image)		F1

Table UC3.5: Details on model definitions and parameters for training and evaluation

As the TBBRDet model itself was mainly developed before the start of the project, the offered customisation for training is focused on [Mayer et al. \(2023a\)](#)'s best-performing model – the Swin-T Transformer. This is actually capable of performing both the object detection and instance segmentation task, which is why an evaluation option is included to allow users to decide on the model focus. The MMDetection toolbox not only enables the initialisation with pretrained weights – here those from the COCO dataset⁴⁰ – but also the continued training of an existing model. Evaluation occurs in line with [Mayer et al. \(2023a\)](#) and focuses solely on AR.

What sets the TASeg model apart implementation-wise are the two libraries made available for training: *segmentation_models.pytorch* ([Iakubovskii 2019b](#)) for conventional CNNs and *transformers* ([Wolf et al., 2020](#)) for the lightweight SegFormer architecture. This grants access to the wide selection of models compared in [Vollmer et al. \(2025b\)](#). Train phases can be chosen based on the previously described “generated” and “manual” datasets, with the “pretrain-frozen” phase automatically initialises with pretrained weights from the ADE20k dataset⁴¹. Various loss functions and hyperparameter definitions can be chosen. The evaluation is quite comprehensive, taking into account various common semantic segmentation metrics.

The focus of the TUFSeg model, on the other hand, lay in studying the impact of feature engineering, specifically different data preprocessing filters, on multi-class model performance. For this reason, only the well-known and high performing U-Net model is made available. The journal publication, [Vollmer et al. \(2025a\)](#), and lesser conference contributions, [Vollmer et al. \(2024a\)](#) and [Vollmer et al. \(2024c\)](#), discuss the details and impact of feature engineering, categorised as platform-specific (vignetting correction) and general enhancement (contrast increase and deblurring). Pretrained weights are based on the ImageNet dataset⁴². Evaluation is again very comprehensive, not only considering common metrics but also weighted and balanced variants to better assess the multi-class aspect given varying class prevalence and occurrence. Additionally, time and energy consumption during training is monitored, the latter by means of *perun*⁴³.

With these descriptions in mind, the importance of a key user story – UC3.E01.US05 “Tracking and comparing experiments” – becomes clear. The platform offers easy access and usage of MLflow for experiment tracking, which was implemented both for the TASeg and TUFSeg models to enable direct model comparisons. With this tool, it is also possible, for instance, to view how each of the three training phases of the TASeg

⁴⁰ <https://cocodataset.org/>

⁴¹ <https://ade20k.csail.mit.edu/>

⁴² <https://www.image-net.org/>

⁴³ <https://github.com/Helmholtz-AI-Energy/perun>

influence final model performance. In more standard models, such as the TASeg implementation, setting up the use of MLflow was quite straightforward. In the case of TUFseg, however, where specialised metrics from *sklearn* were used to provide a broad evaluation, the implementation had to be customised to enable result logging of all 45 metrics. Aside from this, the automatically linked NextCloud storage could again be leveraged to store the trained models in a generally accessible location.

Another training-related user story, UC3.E03.US01 “Training a model by using data of other parties without sharing them”, was optional but nevertheless implemented through the support of KIT-SCC partners. While application I) is based solely on images from one area in a single city (s. [Table UC3.1](#)), application II) uses data from two German cities - Karlsruhe and Munich. This aspect makes for an interesting study concerning privacy issues. Given the nature of the application within the field of energy provision, privacy concerns can arise for DHS network operators if they do not want to share or collectively store their data for combined model training. At the same time, small dataset sizes such as those acquired in Karlsruhe make for a less than optimal foundation for model training on their own. To enable combined training on separate datasets, federated learning via NVFlare⁴⁴ was successfully implemented for the TUFseg model⁴⁵ – the more complex of the two given its non-binary problem definition and skewness among class instance sizes and their occurrence. As highlighted in the conference publication [Duda et al. \(2025a\)](#) as well as other contributions ([Duda et al., 2024a](#); [Duda et al., 2024b](#); [Duda et al., 2025b](#)), federated learning was generally able to contend with the centralised approach. Global and per-client performance was found to depend on aggregation algorithm and workflow – the best choice for the former was found to be FedAvg or Scaffold (conditional upon client number), for the latter Swarm Learning ([Duda et al., 2025a](#)). An additional analysis of energy consumption showed that this aspect is highly setup-dependent, although Swarm Learning was generally found to be the most computationally efficient workflow ([Duda et al., 2025a](#)). With the implementation developed based on this UC, NVFlare was integrated as a platform-wide tool⁴⁶ for general usage.

Service delivery

Service delivery encompasses the provision of the afore-described models themselves. To this end, all three models have been made available as modules on the AI4EOSC Marketplace (see [Figure UC3.1](#)). They can therefore be trained and used for inference by all users.

⁴⁴ <https://github.com/NVIDIA/NVFlare>

⁴⁵ <https://github.com/ai4os-hub/thermal-urban-feature-segmenter/tree/main/nvflare>

⁴⁶ <https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/catalog/tools/ai4os-nvflare>

Figure UC3.1: Modules on the Marketplace associated with UC3

The modules contain details on their usage, including instructional guides, visualisations in form of flyover videos, dataset and code links, and associated publications. Additionally, automatically generated provenance graphs are available for each module, showing how the models are created, what tools are used and which relationships and interdependencies exist on various levels of detail.

Various platform tools and components were leveraged to make the models available in the afore-described manner. The offered AI project templates were extremely helpful for developing modules alongside the detailed AI4OS documentation. All cookiecutter variants included the necessary code for DEEPaaS API integration to connect to standard endpoints while offering different levels of complexity for development. As the first module, the “thermal-bridges-rooftops-detector” was created based on the basic template – a good starting point for initial development with structured guidance. The separate repository code could simply be integrated as a submodule into the API code. The other models were based on the more flexible and customisable “advanced” template – the TUFSeg also via submodule in the “thermal-urban-feature-segmenter” repository, the TASeg directly within the “thermal-anomaly-segmenter”. This UC thereby inadvertently showcases the various ways in which the project templates can be leveraged to achieve successful module integration. Given this foundation, the training platform and all the numerous resources could be leveraged to fulfill UC3.E01.US03 “Provisioning computing resources” which is particularly relevant to the previously described aspect of model training.

An additional benefit of the predesigned templates was the helpful initial structure it provided for code testing. A key user story – UC3.E01.US04 “Performing automated testing” – spoke to the development of reliable software through code testing. To this end, extensive effort was put into writing tests for all endpoint-related functionalities (metadata collection, training and inference). The type of used Python package depended on the cookiecutter template, with the basic one using unittest and the advanced one providing a more complex and extensive code testing foundation via pytest. Together with code style (flake8) and security (bandit) checks, these tests now form the heart of the CI/CD pipeline – another highly relevant tool offered by the platform via Jenkins. The way that Jenkins has been set up to automatically run CI/CD pipelines after new code has been pushed to a module repository means that all changes are immediately checked and problems identified instantly. This process greatly simplifies and alleviates code development and collaboration by ensuring a certain standard as well as functionality.

On this note, another aspect should be mentioned. User support was indispensable for the successful inclusion of the models as modules into the Marketplace. All manner of queries were discussed and solved in our biweekly WP6, bilateral break-out, and in-person user workshop meetings or via e-mail exchanges. These questions went far beyond simple platform issues (such as resource availability or deployment access) and reached from module development, model integration, environment setup, to all aspects CI/CD. The webinars, conference presentations, and tutorial videos in the documentation were also very useful for familiarising oneself with general platform concepts and newer tools.

All model code has been made accessible as modules on the marketplace, meaning the source code and Docker images can be downloaded and descriptive metadata is available. However, a key aspect of service delivery is the usage of the actual model – meaning inference. To this end, the winning model variants as per the mentioned publications are provided via NextCloud, from which they are automatically loaded into the module Docker image and any container built from it. They are thereby made available to all Marketplace users. These variants are:

- For TBBRDet: A Swin-T Transformer achieving 50.7% mean bounding box AR@100 for large thermal bridges ([Mayer et al., 2023](#)).
- For TASeg: A SegFormer with a B2 encoder and Tversky loss function scoring 70.2% IoU, 84.5% F2, 85.9% R, and 79.4% P ([Vollmer et al., 2025b](#)).
- For TUFSeg: A U-Net using the highest resolution TIRs and all possible feature engineering, which – in mean – achieves a 94.9% A, 53.8% balanced A, 57.3% P, 95.4% weighted P, 45.7% IoU, 91.0% weighted IoU, and 94.4% weighted F1 ([Vollmer et al., 2025a](#))

Examples of each of these models' prediction outputs are provided in Figures [UC3.2](#), [UC3.3](#), and [UC3.4](#) respectively.

Figure UC3.2: Example of TBBRDet output of predicted thermal bridge objects / instances, superimposed in green on top of exemplary inputs. The input data consists of RGB (left), TIR (right), and a height map (not displayed here).

Figure UC3.3: Example of TASEg outputs of predicted thermal anomaly pixels, superimposed in red on top of exemplary inputs. The input data consists of full TIR (right) and TIR masked with the DHS pipeline (left) imagery.

Figure UC3.4: Example of TUFSeg outputs of predicted common urban feature pixels, superimposed in colours that match the predicted class on top of exemplary inputs. The input data consists of TIR (left) and RGB (right) imagery.

The availability of these most performant model variants via their Marketplace modules enables UC3.E02.US02 “Analysing images to identify potential problems [e.g. heat bridges, leaks]”, as it allows the models to be used for their designed purpose. This can easily be done by deploying the modules on the Nomad backend, where the provided automatic connection to NextCloud makes it simple to incorporate large amounts of input image data for inference.

While utilising the modules via such deployments directly is easy for users with programming skills, the optional UC3.E02.US04 “Providing a user-friendly GUI for my application to ease access for non-IT persons” specifically spoke to a more easily usable form of implementation. This was fulfilled through one of the newer component incorporations into the platform: the Gradio UI. Accessible for each module via the Try-Me button, this interface is simple to use by anyone regardless of background or skill. The associated deployments are short-term and therefore perfect for testing the models and applications. As such, this functionality simultaneously offers an alternative way of fulfilling the previously mentioned UC3.E02.US02.

The user story UC3.E02.US04 “Integrating with Image Analysis Programs or building additional services on top of the automated thermography service” addressed the more

comprehensive usage of the modules within the applications described at the beginning of [Section 3.3](#). For the stand-alone application I), this was enabled by delivering TBBRDet via OSCAR through the support of the partners at UPV. Aside from the easily usable UI and persistent endpoint exposure for inference, OSCAR includes the additional benefit of privacy features. Building owners or urban planners can analyse their data without having to share either the inputs or the inference outputs. Additionally, Node-RED⁴⁷ and Elyra⁴⁸ custom nodes have been implemented on top of the “thermal-bridge-rooftops-detector” module, which enables users to incorporate the model into any pipelines they might have or plan to develop. Application II), consisting of the TASeg and TUFSeg models, is considerably more complex in terms of data processing and combination. Nevertheless, DHS operators can make use of either or both applications by first identifying thermal anomalies via TASeg, then classifying common thermal urban features as false alarms via TUFSeg. Incorporating this kind of leak detection into their monitoring approaches can greatly increase efficiency and reduce leak costs through timely repairs. By performing regular UAS flights, temporal comparisons can give further insight into network condition and degradation, ultimately providing essential information for effective DHS management.

The final and optional user story, UC3.EO3.US02 “Monitoring the model performance in production”, was implemented for the application II) models given their datasets’ more complex multi-location and multi-class characteristics. In this, the platform tools MLflow and DriftWatch are essential for the logging, storing, and retrieval of relevant training data. Given the dimensionality of the inputs, only multivariate algorithms such as maximum mean discrepancy can be implemented using libraries such as *Frouros*⁴⁹ and *NannyML*⁵⁰. The following experiments are performed:

- Models are trained on a known dataset and tested on unseen data to assess performance degradation, with post-retraining evaluation used to check for data drift.
- Embeddings of trained models are compared with the original variants using e.g. distance-based metrics.
- Potential label drift is investigated by analysing how prediction errors change across classes to identify where drift might be occurring at the class level.

Including these kinds of in-production monitoring methods enables the identification of specific features or classes responsible for drops in performance, for which corrective actions (retraining, data augmentation, model adaptation) can be taken to stabilise inference performance.

⁴⁷

<https://flows.nodered.org/node/node-red-contrib-oscar-thermaldetector-async/in/4pW6ET9DMHs0>

⁴⁸

https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-compose/blob/main/elyra/nodes/async_thermal_detector_async.ipynb

⁴⁹ <https://github.com/IFCA-Advanced-Computing/frouros>

⁵⁰ <https://github.com/NannyML/nannyml>

3.3.2 - Findings and Outlook

This UC furthered the AI-based analysis of thermal images to advance automated thermography as a viable monitoring approach in the field of heat-related infrastructure. As highlighted throughout [Section 3.3.1](#), a research-driven approach was pursued with the aim of not only training AI models to perform the required inference tasks, but to understand the influencing factors and find the most performant variants. The content-related findings of these investigations were documented in the described peer-reviewed publications and other types of conference contributions. Interesting insights gathered during the course of the project were also presented and discussed at webinars to provide newer users with helpful insight into model development and platform usage. For this use case, these included contributions in the ANERIS ([Vollmer, 2023](#)) and second AI4EOSC webinar series ([Vollmer, 2025](#)).

The AI4EOSC platform, tools, and features were imperative in achieving this progress. Specifically, the following components were leveraged:

- NextCloud storage: for storing all three model datasets, all trained models, and the most performant variant for automatic downloading into the Docker images
- AI4EOSC Marketplace: for sharing the three developed modules
- AI project templates: as a starting point for module code development
- DEEPaaS API: as a simple means by which to connect to the platform and make models and key functionalities accessible
- Training platform: for accessing resources and creating deployments with which training and inference (pipelines) can easily be developed and performed
- Jenkins CI/CD: for ensuring code standards and enabling a reliable and automatic software development lifecycle
- MLflow: for storing training experiments, making them easily comparable and thus enabling the following of scientific research principles
- Provenance: for the visualisation of workflows and dependencies characterising all three modules, thus giving new users a transparent overview
- Drift detection and monitoring: for identifying dataset drift, logging detectors, and making methodological as well as temporal comparisons
- Gradio UI (Try-Me): for on-the-fly inference with a nice and easy-to-use interface
- OSCAR: for continuously available inference via remote access or easy-to-use interface, including privacy features
- Federated learning servers: for the training of models on separated sets of data without having to share or combine them, thus overcoming privacy concerns
- AI4OS documentation: as an initial guide and first place to consult in case of issues, esp. the FAQs
- User support: for more in-depth help with all manner of queries and problems

As this list shows, almost all of the existing components described in [Section 2.1](#) were leveraged. The reason why some were not was mainly due to timing. Tools such as CVAT and batch mode, for instance, would surely have been made use of had the related processes (labelling, training) not already been completed before they were introduced as new platform components.

As highlighted in the UC description, a main focus lay on model training and experimentation. In this regard, several findings can be described. Compared to HPC systems such as the bwUniCluster2.0⁵¹ or HoReKa⁵², the platform's offered GPU resources (mainly Tesla T4s) were more limited, both in terms of computing power and capped allocatable RAM. This improved over time as newer and more powerful GPUs (Tesla V100s and a single NVIDIA A100) were introduced. Unfortunately, their limited number and the fact that users retain exclusive access to a GPU for as long as their deployment exists meant that these were quickly tied up. This had a significant impact on experimentation. The training of the TASeg model, for instance, took only around an hour on an A100 GPU, while not having completed after half a day on a T4 deployment. During the course of the project, this issue was partially addressed by enforcing a user-based GPU limit, therefore enabling a fairer distribution of resources. A key advantage of the persistent resource allocation was the fact that continued development and usage was possible at any time without queues or time limits. Additionally, the provided working environments (JupyterLab and especially VS Code) were very user-friendly and enabled code development directly within the deployments.

Recent interviews with DHS operators have shown a rising interest in TIR-based leak detection. Against this backdrop, exploiting the platform in future as well as making it available to end-users would have considerable merit. However, the current readiness level of, in particular, the application II) (s. [Section 3.3.1](#)) combined with the reduced availability of support after the project ends may impede the latter. While the newly introduced ticket system and discussion forum will surely help, the degree of module usage by end-users in future remains open. From a developer's point of view, the platform with its various components, functionalities, and resources offers considerable incentive for future exploitation beyond the end of the project.

3.4 - OPEN-CALL USE CASES

In the second half of the project, when the platform and services approached their mature state after the first release of the platform, AI4EOSC organised an Open call to onboard more communities and researchers. Every application was reviewed individually, and four candidates were selected. These new use cases got full access to all provided services and received similar support as the project use cases.

[3.4.1 - Plant identification on high-resolution mosaics of drone imagery: Mediterranean shrubs and tropical palms \(CSIC, Spain\)](#)

Our project originates from the fact that while very high resolution orthomosaics from drone imagery of vegetated areas have become widespread, appropriate methods for their analysis do not exist. The great improvement in spatial resolution compared to satellite imagery facilitates visual recognition, but challenges classic remote sensing methods. Recent advances in AI methods for image analysis (eg. Segment Anything Model, <https://segment-anything.com/> (Kirillov et al., 2023)) indicate the potential of this approach.

⁵¹ https://www.scc.kit.edu/en/services/bwUniCluster_2.0.php

⁵² <https://www.scc.kit.edu/en/services/horeka.php>

We aimed in our project to apply current deep-learning methods to the specific cases of Mediterranean shrubland and palm trees in tropical forests, taking advantage of existing high-resolution drone orthomosaics.

Achieved results

We decided to start by applying PalmsCNN ([Tagle et al. 2025](#)) to solve the problem. PalmsCNN represents one of the first operational deep learning frameworks specifically developed for palm crown detection in the Amazon, integrating UAV mosaics with extensive ground reference datasets collected in Loreto and Madre de Dios regions of the Peruvian Amazon. PalmsCNN assigns each pixel to class 0 (background) or one of three palm tree species of ecological and economic importance: *M. flexuosa*, *O. bataua* and *E. precatorea*.

PalmsCNN is a two-stage deep learning model that combines semantic and instance segmentation. The semantic module is based on DeepLabV3+ architecture with MobileNet-v2 as backbone and Atrous Spatial Pyramid Pooling (ASPP), which allows capturing multi-scale contextual information while maintaining localization accuracy. This semantic module assigns each pixel to either background or one of the target palm species. The instance segmentation module applies the DeepWatershed Transform ([Bai and Urtasun, 2017](#)) to delineate individual crowns, using distance-to-boundary information to separate overlapping crowns. We note that we have used the semantic segmentation part only in this study.

We conducted our research at the Tiputini Biodiversity Station (TBS), Orellana Province, eastern Ecuador (ca. 0°37' S, 76°10' W; 190–270 m a.s.l., Figure 1). TBS spans approximately 7 km² on the left bank of the Tiputini River, adjacent to Yasuní National Park, within one of the most biologically diverse regions on Earth ([Bass et al., 2010](#)). The study site encompasses a mosaic of forest types characteristic of the western Amazon basin, including not flooded upland forest (“terra firme”), seasonally inundated plain forest (várzea, “inundated”) and permanently flooded palm swamps (“pantano”), which host diverse palm assemblages.

We applied PalmsCNN on 9 subscenes of 4 ha clipped from two sets of drone orthomosaics. The first set of orthomosaics was produced by Gonzalo Rivas in 2023 from photograms acquired using a DJI Mavic 3E platform equipped with a high-resolution RGB sensor (5280×3956 px, 12.29 mm focal length, 3.36×3.36 μm pixel size). Three independent UAV missions were performed across the different forest types: pantano, inundated, and terra firme (Figure 1). All flights were conducted at low altitudes between 82.6 m and 91.2 m above ground to ensure sufficient spatial resolution for detecting individual palm crowns. A second dataset covering the entire extent of the TBS was obtained by Purdue University on 9-11/June/2024 using a DJI Mavic 3 Multispectral UAV platform. Flights were conducted at a constant altitude of 150 m above ground with 80 % forward and 80 % side overlap. The 9 clips span the three main forest types present in the study area. In both mosaics, four clips were selected in pantano, four in terra firme, and one in the inundated forest. This stratified selection allowed us to assess model performance across varying ecological conditions and canopy structures.

Figure OC-UC1.1: Study area within the Tiputini Biological Station, located in the Yasuni Biosphere Reserve, eastern Ecuador, displaying UAV orthomosaics and the boundaries of the analyzed clips covering three forest types: permanently flooded palm swamp (pantano), seasonally inundated forest and terra firme.

Gonzalo Rivas (pers. comm.) provided the reference dataset (named here as the Gonzalo Rivas Point Data- GRPD), which consists of 6685 tree crown points manually marked on TBS orthomosaics. GRPD includes individuals from 28 species, of which 10 are palm species (Table A1). Each observed palm species was assigned a code (1–10). GRPD was reprojected from its original CRS (EPSG:4326) to that of the orthomosaics (EPSG:32718). As TBS and Purdue mosaics are slightly shifted to each other, we created a second version of GRPD for the clips of the Purdue mosaic by adjusting the points to its correct crown.

For validation of PalmsCNN results, we generated 100 random points within each sub-scene and assigned each point to 0 (no palm crown) or 1 (palm crown). In a few cases, the point was placed in a dubious position and was recorded as “invalid”. We recorded the palm species in an additional column: wherever the same palm crown was identified in the GRPD, we kept the corresponding identification. In case the point laid on a palm crown that was not identified in the GRPD, we recorded the point as “unknown” species, except for *M. flexuosa* and *Attalea butyracea* crowns, which we were able to reliably identify on the images. PalmsCNN predictions were compared against the observations in the validation dataset to compute confusion matrices and calculate evaluation metrics

Before the implementation of the UC on the AIEOSC premises for runs over the entire area of interest (TBS), we run PalmsCNN for the 9 selected clips using slightly modified

versions of python scripts provided by Ximena Tagle (author of PalmsCNN), on GEO3BCN-CSIC high-performance computing facility. In these first tests, we proceeded with the PalmsCNN original model, trained in the Peruvian Amazon, thus without additional fine tuning, which we defer for an ulterior study on AI4EOSC premises. PalmsCNN output consists on geotiff raster files with the same geometry of the input clips, in which 0 codes for no palm and integers 1-3 code for each palm species considered by the model: *M. flexuosa*, *O. bataua*, and *E. precatória* respectively.

Findings and Outlook

Figure OC-UC1.2: Examples of crown segmentation results from PalmsCNN: *M. flexuosa* (purple), *E. precatória* (blue) and *A. butyracea* (orange). Validation points from GRPD reference data (yellow) over orthomosaics from TBS (up) and Purdue (down). Subscenes of 50 m x 50 m.

In the TBS clips, 0.009 % of the 900 random validation points (n=8) were excluded due to dubious positioning, and 0.03 % (n=25) were labeled as unknown species. In the Purdue clips, all points were valid, though 0.035 % (n= 31) were labeled as unknown. Palm vs. non-palm identification was always possible, even in the cases of unknown species. The confusion matrices for TBS and Purdue clips PalmsCNN consistently

shows a conservative behavior, with a strong tendency to avoid false positives- only one over 145 palm trees was recorded in the TBS dataset and none in Purdue. However, PalmsCNN tends to underestimate palm abundance (55.6% in TBS and 71.1% in Purdue clips).

Dataset	OA	PA	UA	F1
TBS	0.910	0.444	0.985	0.612
Purdue	0.899	0.289	1.000	0.448

Table OC-UC1.1: Summary of model classification metrics on TBS and Purdue UAV mosaics across 9 clips: Overall Accuracy (OA), Producer’s Accuracy (PA), User’s Accuracy (UA), F1-score.

Figure OC-UC1.3. Observed vs. predicted values for palm and non-palm classes in the TBS datasets. Each point represents a validation subsene, with blue indicating palm and red indicating non-palm classifications. The dashed line represents the 1:1 reference.

At the species level, PalmsCNN achieved an overall accuracy of 91.8 % in the TBS clips after excluding points labeled as “unknown” (n=25; 0.03 %) and as “invalid” (n=8; 0.009 %). Notoriously, none of the predictions for *O. bataua* (class=3) were correct. Instead, 16 of the predictions for *O. bataua* actually corresponded to *A. butyracea* and 3 were classified as “unknown”. We can thus consider that, in this region, PalmsCNN code “3” stands for *A. butyracea* rather than for *O. bataua*. When reinterpreting the results with this adjustment, the overall accuracy of the revised confusion matrix rises to 93.6 %. No crowns of *E. precatoria* were identified by PalmsCNN at the positions of the validation points, but this species was also very rare in the random validation points

(n=1; 0.001 %). Because of their low density in the GRPD none of the random validation points coincided with individuals of *Wettinia maynensis* and *Bactris riparia*. Non- palm and *M. flexuosa* were the only classes with consistent detection: Non- palm achieved excellent performance across all metrics (PA= 0.999, UA= 0.926, F1= 0.961), while *M. flexuosa* showed good results (F1 = 0.845), despite a lower producer's accuracy (0.759), indicating omission errors (Table 8). PalmsCNN produced only one false positive out of 892 validation points across all TBS clips, which corresponds to an individual of *Cecropia herthae*, a non-palm species. PalmsCNN achieved an overall accuracy of 92.9 % on clips of the Purdue mosaic, but at the positions of the random validation points, it detected *M. flexuosa* only, despite 33 crowns of *A. bataua* being actually observed in the validation dataset.

In summary, PalmsCNN with its default model trained in the Peruvian Amazon showed useful and reliable results in the 9 selected subscenes for *M. flexuosa*, the dominant species in the study area, with very few false positives. By contrast, model performance for the other species contemplated by the model (*E. precatorea* and *O. bataua*) was limited. Although PalmsCNN was originally trained to identify *O. bataua*, predictions under this label consistently corresponded to *A. butyracea* in our study area, requiring reinterpretation of the outputs. Additionally, the analysis of GRPD indicated that *I. deltoidea*, which is not contemplated by the current model of PalmsCNN, is a relatively common species in Tiputini across all three forest types.

Therefore, PalmsCNN with its current model can be applied to generate reliable crown cover maps of *M. flexuosa* in the entire region of the Tiputini Biological Station (~7 km²), but it is not suitable for other species. We must fine-tune the model for the species composition of the region.

A major outcome of the AI4EOSC project for us has been gaining an in-depth understanding of how a full AI/ML lifecycle can be organised - from a scientific application prototyping to sharing the application and the inference service, and identifying what tools and services can assist us in this journey. Unfortunately, we are experiencing problems with the PalmsCNN code while attempting fine-tuning, and we have had to postpone the integration of PalmsCNN with the AI4EOSC platform until these problems will be solved. We are confident these challenges will be overcome soon with support from the PalmsCNN author. Meanwhile, additional drone orthomosaics of tropical regions are being produced, which will further increase the value of a shared, robust processing platform such as AI4EOSC.

Looking ahead, we expect AI4EOSC to play a key role in scaling up our work: enabling fine-tuning, supporting multiple users, and applying PalmsCNN to the entire region beyond the 9 subscenes already processed.

[3.4.2 - AI Model for Cracks Detection in Agnostic Environment \(Vertliner, Greece\)](#)

This section provides a summary of the "AI Model for Cracks Detection (Vertliner)" use case. The project's primary goal was to create a highly accurate AI model capable of

automatically identifying and segmenting cracks in RGB images of buildings and infrastructure. The development heavily relied on Python, PyTorch, and significant GPU resources, making the AI4EOSC platform an essential partner for providing the necessary infrastructure for training and experimentation.

The project provides useful R&D and direct advantages for VERTLINER by enhancing the capabilities of its autonomous inspection systems, boosting its competitiveness. Key stakeholders across various sectors—including construction, infrastructure, insurance, and energy—also stand to benefit significantly. The technology will enable them to locate structural defects with greater speed, accuracy, and safety, streamlining their monitoring and maintenance operations.

Achieved results

The project successfully moved from concept to a validated prototype, achieving significant milestones in data preparation, model development, and evaluation.

- **Data Creation and Usage:** We curated a robust and diverse training dataset by combining publicly available crack datasets ([Concrete Crack Conglomerate Dataset](https://data.lib.vt.edu/articles/dataset/Concrete_Crack_Conglomerate_Dataset/16625056)⁵³, [Crackseg9k: A Collection of Crack Segmentation Datasets](https://dataverse.harvard.edu/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.7910/DVN/EGIEBY)⁵⁴), which collectively contain around 20,000 images, with our own proprietary images captured in the field. This blended dataset contains images with resolutions varying from 400x460 to 2560x1440 pixels. To ensure the model's ability to generalize, we intentionally gathered data from various sources to mitigate bias. The data was consistently partitioned into an 80% training set and a 20% evaluation set.
- **AI Model and Performance:** We utilized UNet and SegFormer architectures, with SegFormer-mitb1 serving as our baseline for performance comparison. Key performance metrics included Pixel Accuracy, DICE score, and Intersection over Union (IoU), with the training process optimized by monitoring IoU loss. Our models demonstrated strong performance on both the evaluation set and internal company datasets.
- **Validation and Deployment:** The model was rigorously assessed by our internal domain specialists using datasets relevant to our target applications, confirming its practical utility. While the application has not yet been deployed as a publicly available service, the underlying model has been validated for production readiness.

The AI4EOSC platform was critical to our success. The AI4OS Development Environment, equipped with Dockerized PyTorch 2.1 instances and NVIDIA T4 GPUs, provided the computational power necessary for our R&D efforts. Our data and experiment results were stored in the Nextcloud platform. This access to capable hardware, which we do not own, allowed for rapid prototyping and early results, familiarizing our engineers with cloud-based AI development workflows.

⁵³ https://data.lib.vt.edu/articles/dataset/Concrete_Crack_Conglomerate_Dataset/16625056

⁵⁴ <https://dataverse.harvard.edu/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.7910/DVN/EGIEBY>

Findings and Outlook

Our experience with the AI4EOSC platform was positive, proving to be a stable and powerful environment for our development needs. We utilized the following services to train our AI semantic segmentation models, which significantly boosted our R&D capabilities:

- AI4OS Development Environment
- Dockerized PyTorch Containers
- NVIDIA T4 GPU resources
- Nextcloud for data storage and transfer

The project's progress met our expectations, and while there was a manageable initial learning curve, we would be happy to continue using the platform. The main suggestion for improvement is the inclusion of more powerful GPU hardware (e.g., NVIDIA V100 or A100) to accelerate training times for increasingly complex models. We would be happy to continue using the platform for future projects, especially if more advanced hardware becomes available.

Our future plans are focused on enhancing and expanding the model's capabilities. We will improve the application by experimenting with more advanced network architectures and training techniques. A central part of our strategy is to significantly expand our dataset with more diverse and challenging real-world examples to build an even more reliable model. To engage end-users, we plan to develop a deployable service and integrate the model into a larger structural health monitoring application. This will be followed by targeted promotion to stakeholders in the civil engineering sector and key shareholders in other relevant industries.

3.4.3 - Data fusion based on Machine Learning to increase spectral and spatial resolution in Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 (CSIC, Spain)

This report summarizes the progress made to date on the AI4EOSC Data Fusion use case, which aims to enhance spatial and spectral resolution by fusing Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 imagery using machine learning techniques. It outlines each major step completed, highlights key achievements, and sets the groundwork for the upcoming phases.

This report summarize the status of the different activities proposed in the agreement:

1. Data ingestion from Copernicus services to AI4EOSC storage system
2. Deployment of fusion model at AI4EOSC platform
3. Training, tuning and model validation

Remote sensing monitoring is crucial for a variety of applications, from environmental surveillance to natural resource management. Having images with good spatial and spectral resolution is fundamental for effective tracking of changes in both terrestrial

and marine surfaces, being essential in fields such as coastal monitoring, water quality, and vegetation analysis. However, multispectral satellites like the Sentinel-2A/B twin satellites with high spatial resolution (10, 20, and 60 meters Ground Sample Distance - GSD), provide multispectral images with only 13 spectral bands, while high spectral resolution satellites like the Sentinel-3 mission, with 21 spectral bands, have a minimum spatial resolution of 300 meters. The objective of this use case is to develop a data-driven fusion method that combines the data from these two satellite missions to obtain new products with the best of both in terms of spatial and spectral resolution. For this purpose, a powerful neural network has been trained with data from different latitudes and terrains at lower resolutions. It requires both storage and demanding computing resources, as well as GPUs to train the models.

Achieved results

The Use Case was divided into three different incremental activities.

Activity 1 - Data Ingestion and preprocessing

Data ingestion from Copernicus services to the AI4EOSC storage system. We downloaded 55 Sentinel-2 (L2A) scenes and 55 Sentinel-3 (OLCI/SLSTR, L2) scenes, selected to cover diverse land-cover types (Coast, Urban, Forest, etc.) and paired within ≤ 1 day with low cloud coverage. After ingestion, scenes were co-registered to a common grid, cropped to the Areas of Interest (AOIs), and we certified that the crops still matched after preprocessing (geometric checks and visual verification of overlaps with no noticeable shifts). Storage need (estimate): assuming ~ 0.7 GB per S2 L2A product and ~ 0.3 GB per S3 L2 product, the raw volume is 55 GB. Adding preprocessing derivatives (co-registration/crops) and ML datasets (patches and manifests), we reserve more than 45 GB, bringing the total requirement to roughly ~ 200 GB across object storage (raw + processed + ML dataset). Success criteria are considered met with train/val/test splits materialized and verified.

Before being used for training, a workflow for preprocessing was designed. The preprocessing workflow followed consists of some key steps, that are summarised in the following lines:

- Data collection: we used Copernicus API to obtain the images needed for both training and testing. It was crucial for them to reflect a wide diversity of land features, land cover types, and latitudes, so that the model could generalize effectively. To ensure that images from both satellites were as similar as possible, each image from the Sentinel-3 mission was selected within a maximum one-day window relative to the corresponding image downloaded for the Sentinel-2 satellite. Additionally, to ensure that the images from both satellites were at the same processing level, only Level-1C Sentinel-2 products and Level-1B in Full Resolution Sentinel-3 products were collected. Finally, it was verified that the images did not contain clouds or too many empty pixels.
- Atmospheric corrections: Atmospheric corrections were applied to the images after collection.
- Cleansing and curation: One of the key steps in the data fusion process of the Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 missions was to ensure proper spatial alignment between the images from both missions. Therefore, a coordinate

transformation was first performed on Sentinel-2 images to the EPSG 4326 system. Then, both images were cropped to make them spatially comparable, and the Sentinel-3 bands were resized to ensure a 1:30 pixel ratio between the images.

- **Datasets creation:** To train the networks, it was assumed that the transfer of details from HR bands to LR bands is scale-invariant and depends only on the scale factor between resolutions, which in this case is 30. That is, the mappings 300m->10m and 9km->300m were considered equivalent, allowing the second case to be trained and applied to the first case. Moreover, images were split into squared patches for computational reasons. Finally, the dataset was divided into training, validation, and testing sets.

All the steps were carried out using the AI4EOSC platform. In particular, having our Nextcloud account linked to the deployment was very useful, as it allowed us to store the images there while still processing them with the computational resources available on the platform. With respect to data sharing, we do not intend to publish the data itself, as it was solely used for training the models that will be accessible through the platform.

Activity 2 - Deployment of fusion model at AI4EOSC platform

The fusion model was deployed on AI4EOSC using a containerized Jupyter environment, testing several resource configurations; the optimal setup for experimental training was 50 GB disk, 40 GB RAM, and a GPU (tested on NVIDIA T4 and A100). The AI4EOSC storage was mounted in the runtime so the environment integrates data and models, enabling end-to-end execution from prepared datasets through inference and result export. With this, the success criterion is fulfilled: a cloud-based integrated (data + models) environment that is reproducible.

Activity 3 - Training, tuning, and model validation.

Multiple architectures (CNNs and GAN-style variants) were trained and tuned, with TensorBoard used to monitor runs; MLflow was prepared to manage alternative configurations, though it was ultimately not used for the main runs. The trained models were quantitatively validated using only the downscaled images (those for which target data was available). Four metrics were used, each capturing different aspects of image quality, to ensure more robust results. These metrics were: SRE, RMSE, MAE, and RAE. The results were compared with those obtained using traditional techniques such as bicubic interpolation and pansharpening, with our model outperforming all of them. In addition, a visual evaluation was carried out at both the reduced and original scales, clearly showing an improvement in the predictions of our model over the traditional ones when it came to transferring fine details from Sentinel-2 products to the Sentinel-3 bands.

The manuscript describing the methodology, validation protocol, and results is in final drafting and will be submitted to a journal shortly; the success criterion will be satisfied upon submission and acceptance for peer review

The use case and the way we worked was described in one of AI4EOSC [webinars](#)⁵⁵.

Service delivery

A dedicated [sentinel-data-fusion module](#)⁵⁶ implementing the fusion method has been developed and is available on the AI4EOSC Marketplace.

Users can download the source code directly from the associated GitHub repository, facilitating transparency and reproducibility. Additionally, a Docker image containing the complete environment and application is also provided, simplifying deployment and integration in diverse computing environments.

Through the AI4EOSC marketplace module, users can launch an instance to deploy an API that performs inference with the model. In this setup, via the DEEPaaS API, users provide their Copernicus credentials to download Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 data, a date range to find temporal matches, and an area of interest described as a bounding box with four coordinates (North, West, South, East). From these inputs, the data are downloaded, inference is executed, and a GeoTIFF file is produced containing the 21 Sentinel-3 bands at a spatial resolution of 10 meters.

On the other hand, for more advanced users, the code is available in the AI4EOSC [GitHub repository](#)⁵⁷, and a Docker image with all software requirements and packages is available on Docker Hub for easy access to the entire infrastructure.

Findings and Outlook

The project's progress has been largely in line with our expectations, successfully demonstrating the feasibility of fusing Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 data to generate high spatial and spectral resolution products. Some challenges arose related to the computational demands of training the neural networks and ensuring robust generalization across diverse environmental conditions, but these were effectively managed with available resources.

We are satisfied with the AI4EOSC platform, which provides an integrated environment for data management, processing, and model deployment. Its tools and infrastructure have facilitated efficient experimentation and workflow automation. Support from the developers of the various tools has been very responsive and efficient. The documentation is quite comprehensive, with detailed examples, and the webinars have helped us better understand how it works and how to make the most of the AI4EOSC platform. We look forward to continuing using and contributing to the platform as it evolves.

Future plans include refining the fusion models and improving the atmospheric correction steps to enhance product accuracy. We also aim to develop user-friendly interfaces and visualization tools to engage end-users such as environmental agencies and researchers more directly.

⁵⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Fp75uNtRQ-0>

⁵⁶ <https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosoc.eu/catalog/modules/sentinel-data-fusion>

⁵⁷ <https://github.com/ai4os-hub/sentinel-data-fusion>

3.4.4 - Innovative Marine Resource and Habitat Analysis (IMR, Norway)

This case-study aimed to enhance the speed and accuracy of the data analysis contributing to the characterization of Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VMEs) in Norway. The MAREANO program⁵⁸ collects large amounts of videos (500 – 1TB and 100s of hours) several times a year. Data on the distribution of benthic megafauna must be extracted from these video samples to provide advice to biodiversity managers in the form of maps and reports. The automation of that video analysis is an essential task in the future development of MAREANO. Besides, MAREANO employees are split over many geographical sites and collaborative work necessitates smooth online collaboration and data sharing to be efficient.

Achieved results

In this case-study, we documented the feasibility of transferring such a large-scale workflow from our existing locally implemented prototype into a cloud-computing facility and at a wider scale (analyse more videos routinely) and with as little manual input as possible.

We successfully trained Object Detection models in the AI4EOSC cloud and evaluated the practicality of deploying them on the platform on a regular basis. Large YOLO models were trained in customized Pytorch 2.1 environments, taking full advantage of the GPUs available on the platform at the time and different values for the training parameters were tested to visualise their influence on performances and the maximum accuracies the models could reach. Predictions were also made on large numbers of MAREANO videos and the data is now used in ecological analysis after the raw predictions were downloaded from the platform and integrated into other software. Although the gains in performances compared to leaner models were not game-changing, the benefits of large computing capacity were confirmed. The real improvements, however, were on the logistical and MLOps side of the case-study as the workflow will be much easier to scale-up and repeat on the AI4EOSC platform than on multiple local instances.

Findings and Outlook

Our findings indicate that the AI4EOSC cloud computing facility offered the appropriate level of accessibility to port the MAREANO workflow into the cloud while retaining the appropriate level of control on the data. It is possible for one user without background in computer-sciences to perform the MAREANOs ML workflow in the that same ecosystem with one login, one data storage repository and the possibility to annotate data, train an ML models, evaluate it in a comprehensive and reproducible manner, make predictions at very large scale, and store results in that same environment. All this can be done online and therefore accessible from any terminal with an internet connection hence making collaborative work within the institute much easier.

⁵⁸ <https://mareano.no/en>

We encountered some issues with the platform even though we mostly used its basic features. The deployment of a module or development environment does not always function as expected and the process would freeze at “queuing” or “starting” without a clear reason. We often had to restart them from scratch rather than restore from snapshots. The steep learning-curve associated with the more advanced features (LLM, federated learning...) also made it harder to test them within the short time we had for this case-study. The same could be said about the tools for annotations (CVAT), inference (batch inference, AI4Life...) and UI development (DEEPaaS) which we did not use to their full potential due to the restricted time-frame.

Nonetheless, the possibility to simply train and deploy an ML model in the cloud is important to the smooth adoption of AI into marine research and, thus, gain in efficiency, reproducibility and standardisation. The accessibility of the setup in AI4EOSC could save a lot of time and effort for IMR as users aiming to implement ML, CV or AI can benefit from our acquired experience to emulate the work performed for this case-study, refine and improve it or develop their own for different tasks. All the AI4EOSC features and the potential interoperability it could offer with other European projects will also positively affect future scientific collaborations by smoothing the exchange of data-processing protocols and promoting their standardisation across institutions and countries.

Our findings in this case-study have been used to inform the broader strategy on the implementation of ML and CV that IMR is preparing. Moving forward, IMR will continue to use the platform to not only perform the tasks attached to this case-study but also expand them to other applications of ML models for monitoring ecological and oceanographic processes. IMR is now in talks with AI4EOSC to join the consortium as a resource provider. Computing and storage resources held by IMR will be connected to the platform so that their management (like remote access and login systems, job queuing, hardware allocations etc...) are handled through the AI4EOSC platform and protocols. This will further facilitate porting IMR’s ML and CV workflows into the cloud and optimize the institute’s resources while retaining control over them. The current phase of discussions between IMR and AI4EOSC have focused on the technicalities of that connections for which the AI4EOSC staff have quickly provided guidance to IMR’s IT staff. The process of integration and its details will continue throughout this year and the next as IMR acquires the necessary hardware.

3.5 - AI4LIFE INTEGRATION

AI4Life⁵⁹, a Horizon Europe - funded project to empower life science researchers to harness the full potential of AI/ML methods for bioimage analysis, and AI4EOSC started an effective collaboration at the AI4Life workshop, where AI4EOSC members introduced the AI4OS software stack and the AI platform.

The integration of AI4Life with the AI4EOSC platform demonstrates a successful and scalable approach to interoperability across research infrastructures. This initiative

⁵⁹ <https://ai4life.eurobioimaging.eu/>

aligns closely with the FAIR principles—particularly *Interoperability*—by facilitating seamless collaboration and maximizing the utility of AI/ML/DL models and computing resources across domains.

At the core of this integration is the ability to support and deploy AI models from the BioImage Model Zoo⁶⁰ within the AI4Life cloud marketplace. The process involved ensuring compatibility through clearly defined execution environments (primarily PyTorch), standardized input/output structures enriched with metadata, and uniform prediction pipelines. These specifications enable smooth deployment using a Dockerfile and DEEPaaS-compatible API files.

To streamline the onboarding of external models, a template repository (*ai4os-ai4life-loader*⁶¹) was developed. It automates catalog imports and filters supported models weekly—currently enabling 70 models, with 20 compliant with version V0_5. Users can access the AI4Life dashboard⁶² to deploy any of the supported models and perform inference directly through the platform. Although the platform provides a Gradio⁶³ user interface (GUI), some models in the model zoo use the Segment Anything Model ([Kirillov et al., 2023](#)) model, which requires users to draw bounding boxes on input images. To support this, a custom GUI⁶⁴ was added specifically for the inference of these models, running on port 80.

The user can navigate to the Tools section and select the *ai4os-ai4life-loader*. During deployment, they should choose a model from the provided list. Alternatively, the user can go directly to the Marketplace, open the AI4Life catalogue, and select one of the available models from there ([Figure AI4Life.1](#)).

⁶⁰ <https://bioimage.io/#/models>

⁶¹ <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4os-ai4life-loader>

⁶² <https://ai4life.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/catalog/modules>

⁶³ <https://www.gradio.app/>

⁶⁴ <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4os-ai4life-loader/tree/main/UI>

Figure AI4Life.1: AI4Life catalogue as integration of the Biolmage Model Zoo and AI4EOSC.

3.6 - APPLICATION OF THE LEADING BY EXAMPLE APPROACH

The approach seeks to deliver a reference application illustrating a standard AI module integration within the platform. In AI4EOSC, the primary example of such an application, based on user requirements, is `ai4os-yolo-torch`⁶⁵. It serves not only as a demonstrator, but also is one of the most used general modules since it provides implementation of the YOLO model from Ultralytics⁶⁶ for image and video classification, object detection and segmentation tasks. `ai4os-yolo-torch` repository is based on the AI4EOSC cookiecutter template, the application leverages Nextcloud, integrates DEEPaaS API, and MLflow for experiment tracking, it is containerised and integrated with the platform, and served via OSCAR.

In the course of the project, the YOLO application has been updated to improve compatibility and extend its functionality in two main areas:

3.6.1. Support for YOLOv>=8

Originally provided as YOLOv8, the framework now supports all YOLO versions beyond v8, rather than being limited to YOLOv8. This ensures compatibility with ongoing updates from the Ultralytics YOLO project, allowing users to apply the framework with the latest available models.

- **Previous support:** YOLOv8 only
- **Current support:** YOLOv8 and newer versions (YOLOv>=8).

⁶⁵ <https://github.com/ai4os-hub/ai4os-yolo-torch>

⁶⁶ <https://github.com/ultralytics/ultralytics>

This update simplifies integration with recent versions without requiring major changes to the workflow. The code automatically detects all available YOLO versions provided by the installed Ultralytics package and lists them. The user can then select their preferred version for use and choose to either retrain the model from scratch or fine-tune it.

3.6.2. Hyperparameter Optimization and Experiment Tracking

The project now includes support for hyperparameter optimization using [Optuna](#)⁶⁷ ([Akiba et al., 2019](#)) along with experiment tracking using MLflow.

Features:

- **Optuna:** Provides automated search over training parameters, such as learning rate and batch size, using efficient optimization strategies.
- **MLflow:** Tracks experiments, records configurations and metrics, and allows comparison of results across different runs.

These tools help users:

- Systematically improve model performance
- Reproduce training results
- Manage and document experiments more effectively

4. - USER FEEDBACK STUDIES

The use cases progress, their feedback, and requirements were continuously monitored within the project via bi-weekly meetings, workshops, monthly office hours for open-call use cases, and personal support channels. This section presents studies on the overall satisfaction of the platform-users with the platform itself and the provided support, and the more detailed feedback on the services and tools.

4.1 - GENERAL SATISFACTION

To measure the overall customer satisfaction we handled a survey through Google Forms with the following questions about the AI4EOSC platform and AI4EOSC User support:

- 1) How would you rate your overall satisfaction with the AI4EOSC platform? (scale 1-5)
- 2) How would you rate the following aspects of the AI4EOSC platform? (scale 1-5)
 - a) Ease of use
 - b) Performance and reliability
 - c) Availability of features/tools

⁶⁷ <https://optuna.org/>

- d) Quality of user documentation/tutorials
- 3) How likely are you to recommend the AI4EOSC platform to a colleague or peer? (scale 1-10)

and

- 1) How would you rate your overall satisfaction with the AI4EOSC User Support? (scale 1-5)
- 2) How would you rate the following aspects of the AI4EOSC User support? (scale 1-5)
 - a) Support provided by the team
 - b) Responsiveness of the team
 - c) Knowledge Sharing
- 3) How likely are you to recommend the AI4EOSC User support to a colleague or peer? (1-10)

Meaning of scales:

- Scale 1-5: 1 - very poor (very dissatisfied), 5 - excellent (very satisfied)
- Scale 1-10: 1 - Not at all likely, 10 - extremely likely

Question 3) allows calculating the Net Promoter Score⁶⁸ (NPS) metric as a measure of customer experience and loyalty.

Six platform users from AI4EOSC use cases and three users from open-call use cases participated in the survey. The results and calculated NPS scores are shown in Figures [4.1](#) - [4.2](#) and [Table 4.1](#).

Analyzing the outcomes of the survey, we can highlight that users find their overall experience with the platform to be almost excellent, very much appreciate the availability of features and tools, like the quality of user documentation, and that the platform is generally easy to use. Users are also very satisfied with the provided user support. The NPS scores support the overall high customer loyalty.

⁶⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Net_promoter_score

Overall satisfaction with the AI4EOSC platform

How would you rate the following aspects of the AI4EOSC platform?

Figure 4.1: Results of the survey for the user satisfaction with the AI4EOSC platform (scale 1-5 means: 1 - very poor, 5 - excellent)

Overall satisfaction with the AI4EOSC User Support

How would you rate the following aspects of the AI4EOSC User support?

Figure 4.2: Results of the survey for user satisfaction with the AI4EOSC User support (scale 1-5 means: 1 - very dissatisfied, 5 -very satisfied).

	AI4EOSC Platform	AI4EOSC User Support
NPS score	77.8%	100%

Table 4.1: Calculated NPS score for the AI4EOSC Platform and the User Support.

4.2 - USAGE OF SERVICES AND TOOLS

Another survey to catch the detailed usage of the platform services and tools was conducted. Users were asked on their usage level of every component mentioned in [Section 2](#) and graded in four levels:

- “don’t know about” the component
- the component is “not required”
- user is “considering to use” the component
- user “used/using” the component

The results of the survey are based on eight responses, five from the AI4EOSC use cases and three from open-call use cases. The raw results from the survey are depicted in [Figure 4.3](#). One may see that 60% (twelve out of twenty) of listed components are used by at least 50% of the platform users. However, one has to note that some of the components, e.g. AI4EOSC LLMs, Training in batch-mode, Provenance, or CVAT annotation tools were introduced rather recently. Therefore we combine together the “Used/Using” and “Considering to use” responses together as a popularity metric of the component and sort components by this popularity, which is shown on [Figure 4.4](#). This results in that 90% of the offered components are of interest for at least 50% of use cases, which supports the results of the general satisfaction study in [Section 4.1](#). The most popular ones (at least 75% users are interested in) are:

- Storage
- AI4EOSC Marketplace
- DEEPaaS API
- MLflow - experiment tracking
- Inference with OSCAR
- User support
- AI projects from templates
- Jenkins CI/CD
- Drift detection / DriftWatch
- AI4OS Documentation

Which clearly cover main stages of a typical AI/ML lifecycle with storing data, creating AI projects, training and experiment tracking, sharing on the marketplace, deploying for inference and performing drift detection.

In addition, users were asked the following three questions:

- What do you find GOOD about the platform?
- What do you find DIFFICULT on the platform?
- What do you find MISSING on the platform?

The answers are summarized in [Table 4.2](#) indicating again a general high satisfaction of users with the platform offer but also indicating what can be further improved and what new features could be added.

Usage of AI4EOSC services and tools

Figure 4.3: Raw results of the survey on the usage of the AI4EOSC services and tools (based on 8 responses).

AI4EOSC services and tools sorted by popularity

Figure 4.4: AI4EOSC services and tools sorted by the combined "Used/Using" + "Considering to use" responses (based on 8 responses).

Good	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strongly appreciate that the platform adheres to best practices in data science ● Fusion of all tools and components into one platform ● The platform provides a comprehensive, user-friendly environment for developing, training, evaluating AI models, experiment tracking via MLflow, and serverless inference (OSCAR) ● Availability of GPU-enabled environments ● Found the AI4EOSC team to be responsive and effective throughout the project duration ● Individual component development and maintenance meant dedicated experts were known and could be contacted in case of specific issues ● Cloud-based accessibility which allowed to work remotely and asynchronously ● Significant improvements to the platform's UI during the project helped gain a quicker overview and understanding, such as the inclusion of more detail (i.e., resource usage statistics and module metadata) and new structuring (categorisation by tools)
Difficult	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Complexity and multi-functionality meant a long initial break-in period ● Some of the tutorials and documentation were either too high level, more for advanced users, or some times limited, e.g. for setting up environments, handling data or troubleshooting specific issues ● Managing data storage was not always straightforward or sometimes not persistent ● The user interface of certain components felt unintuitive. A more

	<p>integrated dashboard view of ongoing activities would be helpful</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● OSCAR was a bit difficult to put into operation
Missing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Support for Windows OS would be helpful ● Pre-configured end-to-end pipelines, e.g. for common use cases like image classification, segmentation or NLP ● Improved data management integration, e.g. S3-compatibility or automated dataset versioning ● Having real-time metrics on GPU/CPU usage, memory consumption, job duration, as well as energy usage ● Including more powerful GPUs with fewer memory constraints ● While batch mode partially counteracts resource-“hogging”, it would be helpful to include a GPU queuing method that ensures all users have the opportunity to get more powerful resources, combined with an automatic GPU reclamation after long periods of idle time ● Broader framework support, i.e. environments which would include additional AI libraries (e.g. Detectron2, MMDetection, or HuggingFace Transformers) ● Additional tools for models in production, e.g. active learning (automatic creation of annotations from prediction outputs with minimal human intervention) to retrain and improve models on new datasets. Combined with MLflow and DriftWatch, automatic pipelines could be built that check datasets for drift before initiating retraining and then log and track variants to enable overviews and comparisons. ● Minor dashboard-related aspects to enhance usability, such as indicating current availability in the selection options for GPUs during deployment creation ● Closer link between platform UI and docs to quickly understand each component’s purpose and potential, e.g. by replacing the “Nothing deployed yet” message for unused tools with short “getting started” information boxes including links to docs and webinar / tutorial videos

Table 4.2: User feedback on the AI4EOSC Platform.

5. - CONCLUSION

The deliverable summarizes the progress and results of the AI4EOSC project from a user perspective. The project delivered an advanced platform featuring a comprehensive set of services and tools to support the creation and deployment of AI/ML/DL applications within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Three use cases of the project developed their AI modules extensively using the platform, starting from initial ideas and prototypes, and finished with functional products by the end of the project. Four more open-call use-cases joined the project in the last year to profit from the platform’s offer. Furthermore, an external community, AI4Life, expressed interest in integration with the platform, which was successfully established. The platform was thus validated in practice and aligned with the needs of scientific

communities. Dedicated surveys demonstrated a very high satisfaction of the platform-users with the platform itself and the provided support, and showed that 90% of the platform components are of interest for at least 50% of users.

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